

PROBONO

D1.2 GBN Analysis Tools and Decision Support System

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and/or operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life². Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal³, is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)⁴ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁵ and Renewable Energy Communities⁶ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social co-benefits considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark (2010) established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

¹ Please refer to the last submitted reports for the latest status of the definitions

² <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

³ European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

⁴ SET-Plan Action 3.2: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁵ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁶ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e., cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AEC	Architecture, Engineering, Construction
AECO	Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Operation
AFNOR	French Standardization Association
AWI	Approved Work Item
BEM	Building Energy Models
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BNGI	Building Neighbourhood Green Index
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAG	Chair's Advisory Group
CD	Committee Draft
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DGNB	The German sustainability certification system / German Sustainable Building Council
DIS	Draft International Standard
DLC-BIM	Dynamic Life Cycle Building Information Model
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
DT	Digital Twin
DTS	Draft Technical Specification
EC	European Commission
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FDIS	Final Draft International Standard
GA	Grant Agreement
GB	Green Buildings
GBN	Green Building Neighbourhoods
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IFC	Industry Foundation Class

Acronym	Description
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LLs	Living Labs
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
PC	Project Coordinator
PCC	Project Coordination Committee
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal
PO	Project Officer
PROBONO	The Integrator-centric approach for realising innovative energy efficient buildings in connected sustainable green neighbourhoods
QM	Quality Management
R&I	Research and Innovation
SC	Sub Committee
SF-SSCC	Sector Forum Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
TCC	Technical Coordination Committee
TC	Technical Committee
TG	Task Group
TL	Task Leader
TMB	Technical Management Board
ToC	Table of Contents
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
UBEM	Urban Building Energy Models
UHI	Urban Heat Island
UN	United Nations
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

This document presents the study of the relevant topics related to task T1.1 of the PROBONO project proposal "GBN Analysis tools and Decision Support System" in accordance with the overall framework and aim of the PROBONO project. The report primarily describes some key concepts of GBNs and then focuses on presenting the state of the art of the subtasks defined in task T1.1 towards investigating their *relevance*, *impact*, and *assessment* tailored for PROBONO LLS, as well as their application on specific use cases from PROBONO LLS. The subtasks are as follows:

- a) Human-focused simulation and analysis (PROBONO sub-task ST1.1.1),
- b) GBN Maturity Assessment (PROBONO sub-task ST1.1.2),
- c) Climate adaptation and resilience tool (PROBONO sub-task ST1.1.3),
- d) Biodiversity options analysis (PROBONO sub-task ST1.1.4).

The report contains information on GBNs and their relevant key elements, which makes it relevant for almost all working groups of the PROBONO project, of which WP1, WP2, and WP5 are the first beneficiaries.

1 Introduction

This chapter presents the background and scope of the report in the context of the PROBONO project vision, PROBONO Work Package 1 - WP1 "Macro Knowledge Base and GBN Framework," PROBONO task T1.1 "GBN Analysis tools and decision support system", and the associated deliverable D1.2 report.

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 1.1 - GBN Analysis tools and decision support system	<p>This task includes the following subtasks:</p> <p>Simulation and analysis: Human-focused simulation and analysis for decision support through planning and (early) design of new and renovation of buildings as specified in 1.3.1.1.</p> <p>GBN Maturity Assessment: Provide a GBN Maturity Index tool for GBN initiators to establish a 'greening benchmarking position' and identify technology greening measures against prevailing regulations and financial realities to determine and set realistic GBN targets for the short, medium, and long-term (2025, 2030, 2050).</p> <p>Climate adaptation and resilience tool: Support climate change impacts and risks and specify mitigation and adaptation options taking into account territorial diagnostics, weather and climate data services predictive monitoring, and technology options.</p> <p>Biodiversity options analysis: Adapt the International Biodiversity & Property Council BiodiverCity® schemes in creating GBN environments which accommodate various living nature spaces.</p>	Chapters 2, 3, and 4	<p>A preliminary state of the art to GBN and its key elements such as vision, transition, sustainability, etc., are presented. This preliminary study is followed by presenting the background and context of the related sub-tasks defined in task T1.1 and their assessment and application to PROBONO LLs.</p>
DELIVERABLE			
<p>Deliverable D1.2 – GBN Analysis tools and decision support system (Final)</p> <p>This document is built on the previous (internal) deliverables D1.1(a) and D1.1(b). The report formulates state of the art to GBNs and presents research, application, and design (or, as appropriate, development) of analysis tools and decision support systems consistent with GBN's human-centred, maturity, climate adaptation and resilience, and biodiversity of GBNs.</p>			

Table 1. Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverables & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

The current deliverable is developed related to PROBONO T1.1's (Task 1.1) with a focus on "GBN Analysis tools and decision support system". To begin the journey of developing a GBN, it is critical to understand what value we can generate; how it is measured; how we factor in key dimensions such as biodiversity, climate adaptation and resilience, lifecycle design and operation, investment, and financing; who needs to be involved, and how to begin the overall process. T1.1 contributes to addressing these through comprehensive analysis tools, which provide an initial view used by the project and a concluding view from testing within the project living labs. The scope is, however, set aligned with the four sub-tasks in T1.1:

- *ST1.1.1 Simulation and analysis.* Human-focused simulation and analysis for decision support through planning and (early) design of new and renovation of buildings as specified in 1.3.1.1.
- *ST1.1.2 GBN Maturity Assessment.* Provide a GBN Maturity Index tool for GBN initiators to establish a 'greening benchmarking position' and identify technology greening measures against prevailing regulations and financial realities to determine and set realistic GBN targets for the short, medium, and long long-term (2025, 2030, 2050).
- *ST1.1.3 Climate adaptation and resilience tool.* Support climate change impacts and risks and specify mitigation and adaptation options taking into account territorial diagnostics, weather and climate data services predictive monitoring, and technology options.
- *ST1.1.4 Biodiversity options analysis.* Adapt the International Biodiversity & Property Council BiodiverCity® schemes in creating GBN environments which accommodate various living nature spaces.

PROBONO T1.1 includes three deliverables as follows:

- D1.1(a) Analysis tools specification prior to testing [M6]
- D1.1(b) Tools optimised for LL's following tests [M16]
- **D1.2 Final optimisation following review [M30]**

The scope of the current deliverable report, D1.2, is to bring together and refine the overall work done and provide a sufficient overview of the key topics and areas related to the "GBN Analysis tools and decision support system" in alignment with the overall framework and aim of the PROBONO project.

1.3 Structure of the document and its relation with other WPS/Deliverables

To provide a better alignment between WP1 deliverable reports, Table 2 outlines the structure of this deliverable in more detail in relation to other deliverable reports in WP1.

The report is structured in 5 chapters, with Chapter 1 describing the structure and scope of the report. In Chapter 2, the report begins primarily by defining Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBN) as well as addressing its key concepts and elements such as vision, transition, sustainability, etc., which are eventually an absolute requirement for the development or application or optimizing the current analysis tools and decision support system for transforming the way buildings and cities are designed, constructed and operated. This can also be applied to developments within a rural setting, although this is not described in this report. In Chapter 3, this preliminary study is followed by presenting the state of the art of the related sub-tasks defined in task T1.1 and their link to GBNs and PROBONO LLs. Chapter 4 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of T1.1's subtasks tailored for PROBONO LLs. Finally, Chapter 5 provides information on the applications of T1.1's subtasks to specific use cases from PROBONO LLs.

Corresponding deliverable	Related sections in this document	Description
D1.4: GBN Strategic Vision and KPI Formalisation [C=M32]	Section 2, Section 4	The relevance, impact, and assessment of the subtasks ST1.1.1-3 on the LLs can be used to define and produce the GBN Strategic Vision and KPIs partially.
D1.6: GBN Scenario Generation and Strategic Case Studies [B=M40]	Section 4, Section 5	The relevance, impact, and assessment of the subtasks ST1.1.2-3 on the LLs and used case outcome can be used to partially develop the GBN Vision into practical intervention scenarios.
D1.9: GBN Transition Challenges, Enablers & Future Roadmap [E=45]	Section 4, Section 5	The relevance, impact, and assessment of the subtasks ST1.1.2-4 on the LLs and used case outcome can be used to partially identify GBN's transition challenges, enablers, and future roadmap.
D1.12: GBN Integration Strategies and Transition Models [D=M48]	Section 4, Section 5	The relevance, impact, and assessment of the subtasks ST1.1.2-3 on the LLs and used case outcomes can be used to partially develop clear strategic plans for implementing the LL Target Model GBNs.

Table 2. Structure of this deliverable in relation to other deliverables in WP1

1.4 Contribution to creating GBN

The PROBONO project vision is a people-focused European construction industry working in harmony with the broader community of stakeholders, including public authorities and citizens, to deliver *scalable, sustainable, and viable energy-positive and zero-carbon **Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN)***. In line with the overall PROBONO project vision, and as part of PROBONO WP1 on “Macro-Knowledge Base and GBN Framework”, the current report aims to address multiple key concepts and elements that can be exploited in creating/developing the current/future GBNs such as vision, transition, sustainability, etc. On the other hand, the outcome can potentially be exploited as a prerequisite for the development and application of analysis tools and decision support systems in the GBN context, with a focus on human-focused simulation and analysis, GBN Maturity Assessment, climate adaptation and resilience tool, and biodiversity options analysis, which are the major focus of the report.

2 Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs)

This chapter presents the evolved view of Green Building Neighbourhoods (GBNs), the main focus of the PROBONO project. It includes key aspects and elements such as vision and target model, stakeholders, sustainability, transition and integration, etc., which are prerequisites for developing and applying analysis tools and decision-support systems in the context of GBNs and on different levels.

2.1 GBN definition

2.1.1 GBN definition according to EU

Under the European Green Deal call H2020-LC-GD-2020 (topic LC-GD-4-1-2020), “green neighbourhood” is defined as follows:

“The term ‘neighbourhood’ refers to a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than the one of a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A ‘green neighbourhood’ is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish (e.g. soft and zero-emission mobility, renewable energy, bioclimatic architecture, etc.)” [1]

2.1.2 The GBN Target Model: What is it, why is it needed, and how do we build it?

The Conceptual GBN. A GBN – Green Building Neighbourhood, is a concept under development by the Probono H2020 project [2] funded under the EU’s Horizon 2020 programme in support of the Green Deal. PROBONO’s early-stage, conceptual description of a GBN states:

A GBN is an ecosystem of Natural, Physical, Technical and Social attributes, interacting within a wider System of Systems. A GBN aligns the human and natural world, reducing energy use through renewable, local sources and circular resources. A GBN aspires to a net positive impact on both humans and nature, operating in line with both the natural world and urban reality. It is an urban or rural ecosystem, that minimises human impact on the natural world, balancing both development and Quality of Life. A GBN is a people-centred social, urban and natural area, integrating natural and human infrastructures, through positive and sustainable collaboration.

At a conceptual level, all communities are nascent GBNs, and this description provides a clear and aspirational narrative to support them mature. In practice, in real-world terms, how this

aspiration translates and comes together on the ground remains pivotal, in particular, its application, value and benefit to those seeking to make and mature the GBN journey for their particular neighbourhood (or community).

The Practical GBN. A GBN, through its data, tools and techniques, is the translation of the Green Deal policies, through practical innovations and activities, implemented at neighbourhood levels. The Green Deal states, *“EU countries are committed to achieving climate neutrality by 2050, delivering on the commitments under the Paris Agreement. The European Green Deal is the EU’s strategy for reaching the 2050 goal. It supports the transformation of the EU into a fair and prosperous society with a modern and competitive economy.”*[3].

By identifying the range of activities under the Green Deal that can be translated to a neighbourhood level, benefitting local context and needs, a GBN, in parallel, creates an enabling bridge between building-level renovations and city-wide plans. *A GBN becomes a sustainability accelerator at the neighbourhood level, supporting city-wide aims.*

With the Green Deal covering: *climate, the environment, energy, transport, industry, agriculture and sustainable finance*, the data, tools and techniques used to develop a GBN, provide decision-makers, local actors and stakeholders with the means and best practice approaches to understand the range of options available to them and their neighbourhood. Then, how they can plan, participate and measure these to achieve their sustainability aims through their own locally relevant GBN. In addition, GBN planning tools also help decision-makers identify and facilitate the key supporting mechanisms that make a GBN possible: Green finance, commissioning, procurement and economic options and models, for example. Also, addressing how a GBN might be coordinated, managed and governed through, for example, the role of a GBN Integrator.

The Target (Model) GBN. PROBONO has 6 Living Labs (LL): Madrid, Dublin, Porto, Aarhus, Brussels and Prague [4]. Each is renovating buildings at varying scales and testing various technology and social innovations to meet its renovation and sustainability needs. None is a mature GBN. The intent is to show how its technology and innovations will contribute to informing its transition and integration towards potentially becoming one.

There is a need for a reference - a GBN Target Model, where a range of Green Deal initiatives has, or is, being carried out, with sustainability objectives and ambitions clearly set out and supported at political, social and economic levels. Our Madrid LL, the Madrid Nuevo Norte (MNN) [5] development, is the most significant urban transformation project that Spain’s capital city will undergo, and one of the most important in Europe. It is designed to improve citizens'

life quality and create a more efficient, sustainable, and prosperous people-centred city, where public spaces, sustainable mobility, housing, offices, retail spaces, green areas, and public facilities are complementary. A model designed through citizen participative processes provides a reference for what a mature GBN Target Model might look like.

The Madrid GBN (Our ambition for it). The PROBONO LL in Madrid is a relatively small part of MNN, focused on the Las Tablas district [6]. It forms an integrated, integral part of the entire MNN development and wider sustainable ecosystem. It showcases a geothermal energy model as a basis for going beyond zero CO2 emissions, establishing a positive energy balance through feasible technological and social solutions for both individual buildings set within broader green districts.

The following activities are carried out to establish our GBN Target Model: a deep literature review and desk analysis of both MNNs and wider Madrid's sustainability activities to establish a Green Deal initiative baseline. Followed by the application of both EU City Calc [7] and ISO 37101 [8] mapping (forming PROBONO's GBN maturity assessment tool) to assess both Las Tablas and MNNs activities against local/regional context and aims and national/international 2050 targets. In addition, Net Zero Cities [9] initiatives aligning with the planning and development needs of a GBN will be considered (5 PROBONO LLs, including Madrid, are Net Zero cities). Together, these provide a robust understanding of a GBN reference model. This GBN reference model will be assessed against the PROBONO LLs (adapted to the local context) and their Net Zero City initiatives, producing a gap analysis of the maturity of each LL towards their GBN journey. A GBN transition and integration strategy contextualised for each neighbourhood LL is then produced. The outcome is presented in more detail in deliverables D1.11 and D1.12 reports.

The proposed GBN Target Model gives a scalable, transferable benchmark and framework incorporating the political, economic, social, and environmental objectives desirable for a GBN. Furthermore, supporting the design of a systematic and holistic methodology for transitioning to sustainable and fair neighbourhoods. This can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed GBN Target Model

2.2 Introduction to GBN sustainability

There is not yet a clear understanding of what sustainability means and entails in the context of GBN. In recent years, the AEC industry (architecture, engineering, and construction) and researchers have developed a basic understanding of sustainability and its practices and have found a common language for working with sustainable development of the built environment. An important part of this is bridging the gap between industry, research, and policy institutions to ensure that the transition is moving in the same direction.

Sustainability can be considered intangible since prior work has shown that it can be hard to quantify and difficult to measure since it can contain many different perspectives. Ever since the Brundtland report [10] (Our Common Future, was presented in 1987), “*sustainability has been defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*”. Furthermore, the Brundtland report also presented the first framework to describe what sustainability included in the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) and the three pillars of sustainability: social, economic, and environmental. The framework had a more holistic approach to the sustainable term involving the obvious environmental means and considering the social and economic dimensions to establish the trinity of sustainability.

Environmental sustainability aims to restore and maintain harmony between nature and the built environment. This includes the building's impact on the climate, from construction to operation and maintenance. Emphasis is placed on the efficient use of natural resources, reusability and recycling, thus minimising the overall environmental impact of the building. It also preserves biodiversity and avoids the use of materials with high toxicity and scarce resources. The goal is to reduce the environmental impact at local, regional, and global levels through the consumption of energy, water, and resources during the different phases of the building's life cycle [11, 12].

Economic sustainability is essentially concerned with ensuring holistic decision-based quality in price and materials from a long-term perspective that strives to cover the balance between expenditures and the quality achieved over the life of the building. This is framed by calculating the total cost of ownership (TOC) of the building, which relates to the construction of the building and its operation. This involves taking a long-term view of the building to optimise construction and operating costs while ensuring value stability for the future. Economic sustainability considers the initial cost and expenses for years to come. The TOC helps determine whether the additional cost of higher-quality materials will pay off. So, it is not about choosing the cheapest short-term solution, but the solution that delivers the greatest long-term benefit with a holistic perspective [11, 13].

Social sustainability focuses on human relationships as human health and well-being. In relation to buildings, creating a comfortable and safe environment also considers the social interactions in and around the building. Thus, it considers a broader range of social and societal perspectives to accommodate the diversity of people. These include indoor climate, working environment, architecture, functionality, accessibility, adaptation to the local environment, and user comfort [14].

The three areas are correlated and must be used with one another. Thus, there must be a balance between the three areas to obtain true sustainability. This is even still that most often, the correlation of the areas also will contradict each other, i.e., if sustainability increases in terms of environment, it might be worse from an economic perspective. Therefore, using the TBL framework to determine sustainability prioritises a trade-off between the areas. However, in general, a sustainable solution should represent all three areas of TBL. The more balanced, the better from a more neutral standpoint, but the context in which it is applied often determines how the trade-off prioritising is allocated the best. In building design, it can be referred to as the outcome of a particular set of values focusing on increasing the efficiency of resource use (i.e.

energy, water, materials) while reducing building impact on human health and the environment during the building's lifecycle through better siting, design, construction, operation, maintenance and removal (US-EPA 2013)¹⁰.

The TBL needs to be included in the paradigm shift to a more holistic way of thinking that envisions a more comprehensive solution and includes the three dimensions in the long-term perspective. This should lead to choosing the optimum solution for each situation from a broader perspective and not just considering the obvious and intuitive solution. Instead, this should be embedded in the whole process to have a better informed and sound basis that can be used, especially in the planning and design phase of buildings and neighbourhoods, to create a better basis for a project. This includes a more systematic approach with transparency and traceability of solutions and decisions. This has been shown to be less costly and challenging as it impacts initial decision-making and better defines the project in the early stages. This gives a more integrated process (refer to Integrated Design processes - IDP), having defined the project at a higher degree, to mitigate the changes to the project during early stages, due to higher impact and ability to control project costs of such solutions, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Decision impact and cost through project stages (source: [15])

2.2.1 Sustainability certification systems (e.g., DGNB)

There are a number of different certification schemes that have been developed and applied to measure and document the sustainability aspects and characteristics of buildings and built environments. In recent years, building certification systems have been the first step in guiding the construction of sustainable buildings. Certification systems have transformed sustainable

¹⁰ source: https://cfpub.epa.gov/si/si_public_file_download.cfm?p_download_id=520120&Lab=NHSRC

building into a manageable and systematic process that combines all the necessary work into one framework to ensure that sustainability is addressed at all project stages. The certification system must be followed and adhered to receive certification at the end of construction. Building certification includes consideration of sustainability throughout the construction process. This includes considerations in the early design phase, the construction phase, and the execution phase to see the impact later in the operation and maintenance phase after the building is completed. Certification schemes allow all project stakeholders to work within a common framework with a more systematic approach to sustainable solutions while meeting the actual criteria for sustainable construction.

Furthermore, it ensures that the sustainable mindset is holistically kept throughout the whole project life cycle. Certifying a building does not itself ensure that the building is sustainable. However, it forces the decision-makers and designers to make active choices in the building's scope and early design phase. Based on this, by acquiring a certification, it raises the overall quality of the building concerning sustainability. The integration of certification systems benefits construction projects in the early design phase as the project's foundation is made with key action points such as the selection of design, products, materials, etc. These are decisive for further developing the project stages and can be reflected in the final building. Furthermore, it provides the basis for a common project language while ensuring necessary documentation and data to ensure transparency throughout the remaining processes[14].

As of today, there are many different building certification systems available worldwide, with some being more frequently used than others, depending on the national context. The most well-known sustainable building certification systems worldwide are LEED (US) [16], BREEAM (UK) [17], and DGNB (Germany) [18, 19]. The first two were also the first building certification systems presented in the 1990s. Today, LEED and BREEAM are also the building certification systems most applied globally, based on their acknowledgement from the international perspective. DGNB is spreading and receiving more attention in the EU. Many countries use the certification systems which are the best fit for their building regulation, norms, and traditions. This implies that the certification system may be adjusted to fit the national context better and consider the certifications developed regarding the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive. However, which certification system is the best and should be used depends on the context and purpose [14].

The certifications mentioned above all have in common that they rate a building based on an evaluation matrix, whereas different levels are obtainable depending on the score. The score

reflects the degree of sustainability in the building according to the certification system and is rewarded with a certificate. The higher the score, the better the certification level. Table 2 presents a comparison between four certification systems commonly used in the EU, and as such, the different certification systems' focus points and how the scoring system is formulated and rewarded are summarised ([20] based on [14]).

	BREEAM	LEED	DGNB	Nordic Swan
Focus point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management - Health and well-being - Energy - Transport - Water - Materials - Pollution - Innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location and Transportation - Sustainable Sites - Water Efficiency - Energy & Atmosphere - Material & Resources - Indoor Environmental Quality - Innovation - Regional Priority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental quality - Economical quality - Social quality - Technical quality - Process quality - Area quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy and resources - Indoor environment - Materials and chemicals
Score system	%-score 0-100	Score points 0-100	Score points 0-100 %	Pass / Fail
Certification level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outstanding - Excellent - Very Good - Good - Pass - Acceptable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platinum - Gold - Silver - Certified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platinum - Gold - Silver 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nordic Swan ecolabel
Approx. Certification fee	8.200-35.000 (DKK) [~ 1100-5000 (EUR)]	3.150-200.000 (DKK) [~ 500-27000 (EUR)]	18.500-550.000 (DKK) [~ 2500-74000 (EUR)]	11.000-250.000 (DKK) [~ 1500-33500 (EUR)]
Sustainable focus categories				
Environment	66%	68%	33%	83%
Economic	5%	2%	30%	1%
Social	29%	30%	37%	16%

Table 2. Certifications focus summary [20] based on [14])

All the certification systems have their primary focus on the new construction of buildings and are relevant for existing buildings and renovations. They can also be applied on district scales. Currently, LEED, BREEAM, and DGNB have been found to be most useful for larger building

projects due to the expensive documentation required. Even though the certification may have different focal points and criteria weightings, they all bring the sustainable construction agenda into the project stage, facilitating a sustainable solution to be made in the early design phase to lower the CO₂ emission and increase resource efficiency.

The expenses of applying a certification system are more likely to be justified in a larger project, with the size and ambition of the building. The Nordic Swan is most applicable for houses and residential construction, focusing on toxicity and material quality. How holistic the certification systems are can be seen in Table 2. Most notably, in the BREEAM, LEED, and Nordic Swan [21], the economic aspect is almost not considered, whereas the DGNB has a more holistic approach with a more even division. The DGNB is regarded as one of the most comprehensive certification systems that almost equally consider the three pillars of sustainability, including social, economic, and environment [14].

2.3 Introduction to GBN Stakeholders

The importance of engaging and involving stakeholders is a well-known and commonly acknowledged key to the success of any business or project. Hence, when designing, implementing, and operating a complex entity such as a GBN, one needs to consider carefully who the stakeholders are and how to engage them to build a sustainable GBN both economically, environmentally, and socially.

During the past 40 years, stakeholder theory has developed drastically, as shown by Freeman et al in *Stakeholder Theory: State of the Art* [22]. The traditional narrative guiding our understanding of stakeholders and stakeholder engagement in the sphere of business and project management has been an understanding of stakeholders as individuals competing over limited resources, associated to a conceptualization of value as a fixed asset in a zero-sum game. However, the understanding of value has turned towards the concept of *value creation*, stressing instead the social nature and processes of creating value in society (Freeman et al. [22], pp. 280-281). In their elaborated work on stakeholder theory, Freeman et al. [22] argue that a guiding principle for stakeholder engagement should be to approach individuals as “*working together to create sustainable relationships in the pursuit of value creation*” (ibid. [22] pp. 280).

Approaching value creation as a social process is advantageous for the present purpose. GBNs are complex entities with a diverse group of stakeholders, including both public, private, and civil organisations, institutions, and businesses, as well as private citizens, e.g., as end-users of

technological solutions. As the success of the GBN will depend on the implicit and/or explicit support of these stakeholders, it is crucial to seek solutions that are valued and agreed upon by all stakeholders.

2.3.1 GBN stakeholders

As part of the project proposal writing phase, a preliminary map of GBN stakeholders was produced (see. This map was created from previously identified roles and responsibilities of the principal stakeholders within any given neighbourhood, involved in developing, implementing and managing aspects that impact upon the daily lives of citizens and communities in terms of quality of life, well-being, sustainability and resilience. They were further developed for the PROBONO proposal through the addition of the two roles of the GBN integrator and the mediator which will be commented on below. As the development, implementation and subsequent operation of a GBN needs a high degree of collaboration, coordination and collective effort across all those stakeholders involved, impacted and eventually benefiting from a GBN, the two roles ensure that the combined effect of the collective effort is optimised to deliver maximum effect.

As described in deliverable D1.1 report, a preliminary map of GBN stakeholders was developed (see Figure 3) based on the roles and responsibilities of the key actors in any neighbourhood. Two new roles were introduced for the PROBONO proposal: the GBN integrator and the mediator. These roles facilitate the coordination and optimization of the collaboration among all stakeholders in a GBN.

Based on the 40 stakeholder interviews and Living Lab workshops (see *D2.1: Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping*, Section 2.2 for a full introduction to the process), this map has been adapted to map the current understanding of the GBN stakeholders. The stakeholder categories will be commented on briefly in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Map of GBN stakeholders

The stakeholder map is centred around the *GBN Integrator*, as the individual or collaborative institutions, organisations or persons responsible for planning and driving the development of a GBN forward to accelerate the sustainability abilities and ambitions of a neighbourhood. One thing to note is, that depending on how the GBN is initiated (is it a public procurement process or a citizen-led initiative?) the GBN Integrator may shift over time as the requirements for this role will change. Table 3 below shows the different roles of the stakeholders and some of the tasks they are responsible for.

Stakeholder	Role	Responsibilities
GBN Integrator	Drives GBN development	Responsible for planning and driving the development of a GBN forward to accelerate the sustainability abilities and ambitions of a neighbourhood
Mediator	Engages local resources	Leverages existing trusted local resources for the engagement with local citizens and business
Local Authorities	Key partner for obtaining permissions, grants, funds and implementation	Provides necessary permissions, grants or funds for GBN activities, as well as guidance and implementation. Relevant departments could be Urban Planning Department, Social Department, Environmental Department, Housing and Construction Department.

Stakeholder	Role	Responsibilities
Private financing	Private financing	Provides private financing for investments in building renovations or funding for community activities. Sources could be private funds, financial institutions, investors, pension funds
Public Funding	Supports research and innovation	Provides public funding to support research and innovation activities as part of the GBN development. Sources could be public funds (local, national, international) or public loans
Local Business	Ensures sustainable economy, participates in GBN activities	Engages in GBN activities such as energy communities, building renovations, sustainable festivals, sustainable procurement etc. to ensure a sustainable local economy. Should include both small and large-scale businesses
Citizens	Key partners in community building	Partners and drivers in community building centred around sustainable living, including energy renovations, circular economy, changing transportation modes etc.
Developers	Catalyst for sustainable development	Identification and driver of sustainable renovation/new development within a neighbourhood
Construction Companies	Deliver building refurbishments	Partners in delivering building refurbishments for GBN development
Utilities Companies	Secure sustainable resource use	Partners in securing sustainable use of resources, clean water and energy etc.
Technology Suppliers	Deliver smart solutions	Partners for delivering smart solutions for sustainable cities, e.g., for EV charging, energy exchange, energy passive buildings, virus control, resource management
Other Suppliers	Could include architects for GBN design	Could include architects delivering the design of the GBN

Table 3. Overview of stakeholders, stakeholder roles and stakeholder responsibilities

2.4 Introduction to GBN transition

GBNs as part of sustainable building initiative are answers to the climate change, we experience. Through the last years, we realised the impacts of this phenomenon on our daily lives and therefore decided to act upon it by adapting to it.

In order to face the transition from a rather stable and known climate to a more intense and extreme one, we have to transit to a way of living as we know it to new one better fitting to these new circumstances.

GBNs are delimited areas that include appropriate infrastructures, mobility policies, energy resources and consumption that support the transition toward a more sustainable way of living. This change impacts the various aspects of the community as presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Sustainable Urban Neighbourhood [23]

As we transit to this next way of living, every aspect of the life of a community will also have to shift. But as the process is taking its course, its original purpose shall not be forgotten.

As most industries, the building industry is mostly led by a short term and cost reduction approach that doesn't not seem to always align with the objective of a green based neighbourhood. However, in the face of recent years, we experienced higher temperatures, droughts, intense rainfalls, floods, landslide and more events that emphasized the need to create living systems that are more resilient to these phenomena but also create less CO2 emissions and that consume less energy by optimising its use.

According to the European Union Commissioner for Energy [24]:

“Buildings are the single largest energy consumer in Europe, using 40% of our energy, and creating 36% of our greenhouse gas emissions. That is because most buildings in the EU are not energy efficient and are still mostly powered by fossil fuels. We need to do something about this urgently, as over 85% of today's buildings will still be standing in 2050, when Europe must be climate neutral. Improving our homes is also an effective response to high energy prices – the worst-performing buildings in the EU consume many times more energy as new or properly renovated ones. And it's often the most vulnerable who live in the least efficient houses and therefore struggle to pay the bills. Renovation reduces both the energy footprint of buildings and the energy costs for households, while also boosting economic activity and job creation”.

At the scale of the European Union, the 2020 approved Green Deal (see Figure 5) is a set of policy which aims at making the European Union climate neutral by 2050. With a 30 yearlong action window, the European Union plans on reducing the greenhouse gas emission by working on several action levers such as circular economy, building renovation, biodiversity, innovation and more.

Figure 5. The European Green Deal¹¹

¹¹ source: <https://euinasean.eu/eu-green-deal/>

In most cases, emissions reductions initiatives in the construction sector were focused on the buildings' operational phase, whereas in the Green Deal, one of the key initiatives is to achieve energy efficiency by renovating both public and private sector. The "Renovation Wave" as it is presented on Green Deal page of the European Commission website stated the following objectives to enhance the quality of life for people living in it while creating additional jobs in the sector:

- Tackle energy poverty and worst-performing buildings
- Decarbonising Heating and Cooling
- Renovate public buildings and social infrastructures

Furthermore, the European Commission supports research and innovation in these sectors through different programmes such as:

- The BUILD UP initiative which promotes knowledge sharing on energy-efficient building
- The BUILD UP Skills initiative which emphasizes on the number of professionals across Europe specialized in high energy performance renovation
- The 4RinEU project which presents innovative tools and strategies encouraging large scale innovation of existing buildings and also promotes the use of renewable energies

Several countries in Europe have also started to implement legal frameworks setting buildings codes and CO₂ emissions. As examples from [25]:

- The Netherlands introduced CO₂ limits for all new residential and non-residential buildings
- Denmark introduced CO₂ limits for all new buildings over 1000 m²
- France introduced CO₂ limits for all new buildings
- Finland and Sweden are planning to introduce CO₂ limits for all new buildings

When it comes to Green Buildings Neighbourhood itself, some countries in Europe have already started to experiment this transition [26], among others, are:

- BedZED in Sutton, United Kingdom. This 2002 neighbourhood was created with the objective of designing a housing complex which consumes zero fossil fuels during its life period by combining solar panels, triple-glazed windows and 50-centimetre-thick walls filled with natural insulating materials.
- BO01 in Malmö, Sweden is a neighbourhood 100% powered by renewable energy sources and linked by a network of electric buses.

- Zac de Bonne in Grenoble, France gathers low-consumptions buildings powered by solar thermal panels that are shared between social housing, a school, a nursery, a cinema and a shopping centre.

As a result, from those experimental implementations, multiple countries in Europe have individually created their label identifying sustainable neighbourhood to promote those initiatives. For example, in France there is the “EcoQuartier” label, when Belgium works with the “Quartier Durable” label. Just as a brand name, these labels promote transition towards this new model of neighbourhoods at the scale of the country they are implemented in.

As we move forward, it becomes clear that a synergy of information, knowledge, good practices and guidelines is mandatory to achieve this common goal. As for now, we identified numerous innovative practices, methodologies, standards and certifications.

Yet, a detailed and joint book of standard policies stating which criteria to respect and performance to achieve must be consider to ease this transition and help channel the momentum in the fit direction.

Moreover, the topic of funding and therefore the implementation of the new standards and policies aligned with more sustainable buildings are also at the core of this transition. As an example, the Just Transition Fund (JTF) is a tool to promote transition towards climate neutrality for the countries that are the most impacted by climate change.

This fund was created under shared management and aims economic stability, jobs creation and protection but also the transformation of existing carbon-intensive facilities and a significant emission reduction.

Practically however, some tensions around the allocation of the Just Transition Fund arised the following years after its creation highlighting the complexity of the implementation process of this transition at a large scale.

2.5 Introduction to GBN standards

Standardization in a research and innovation (R&I) project offers many advantages for the project. By developing a standardization strategy in R&I projects the transfer of project results into standardization is aimed. This leads to the practical applicability and reproducibility of the project result. Further, standardization also means the involvement of relevant stakeholders

from outside the project ensuring the achievement of a broader acceptance of the project results.

In general, standardization activities in R&I projects are divided into three steps:

1. Overview of the standardization landscape
2. Identification of standardization potentials
3. Initiation of standardization activities

In a first step of standardization in an R&I project, it is always important for all the partners to get an *overview of the standardization landscape* concerning the project to avoid inventing the same wheel again and to raise awareness to what is already on the market. Therefore, with specific keywords given by the projects partners a list of standards is created which seem to have a connection to the project. The project partners are asked to identify the standards which are or could be relevant for the project. The result is an overview of all the standards identified as relevant or interesting for the project. This should be the basis for working with standards during the duration of the project and will be updated continuously. This overview is also the basis for the following actions regarding standardization. At this point an insight into the world of standards and the standardization work is given. In a second step the standardization potentials are analysed. Within a *standardization potential* workshop with all project partners as important identified standards are compared with new potential topics where standardization would be interesting for the project partners. Moreover, the opportunity is given to express interest on a liaison with relevant standardization committees. In this step with the focus the end-user needs a standardization strategy is defined to implement the identified potentials. The third step is the conduction of *standardization activities*. Via liaisons input to already existing standards and ongoing standardization activities is foreseen. In this step, based on the identified new potentials the initiation of new standards, e.g., CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA) follows. Further, standardization roadmaps can be developed. The developed standards can also be disseminated and promoted.

In PROBONO it is planned to start the work in T9.4 *Standardization activities* with a short survey on if and how PROBONO project partners are already involved with standardization and if they are interested in specific areas regarding standardization. This is necessary, because PROBONO is quite a big R&I project with a variety of different stakeholders and a wide focus on green building neighbourhoods (GBN). GBN cover a broad field of topics and it appears to be user-oriented to focus at first on specific subject areas for the state-of-the-art standardization landscape analysis. Consequently, in this section as a first step regarding the standardization

activities in PROBONO a general overview of the topic of sustainable cities regarding standardization is given.

In general, for a first overview of standardization, it is necessary to have a look at the Technical Committees (TC) on international and European level. The TC's develop standards, reports and specifications with the aim to facilitate the cooperation and communication between different stakeholders. To develop those documents the TC's bring together experts to agree on the different kind of requirements. Hence, to get an overview of what is going on regarding standardization, it is important to know which TC's are doing the relevant work. Since this section of the deliverable should just give a general overview of what to take care of when talking about standards in the context of GBN only the most important TC's are considered in more detail.

On international level, the most relevant TC in a general sense is ISO/TC 268 *Sustainable cities and communities* where the secretariat is hold by AFNOR (France). With the development of this committee in 2012 the standardization in the field of sustainable cities and communities started. The scope of this TC is standardization in the field of Sustainable Cities and Communities including the development of requirements, frameworks, guidance and supporting techniques and tools related to the achievement of sustainable development considering smartness and resilience. This is intended to help cities and communities as well as other interested parties in rural and urban areas to become more sustainable.¹² In doing so, ISO/TC 268 contributes to the UN Sustainable Development Goals especially goal 11 which aims to make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.¹³ ISO/TC 268 has 40 participating members and 31 observing members. The structure of this TC is displayed in Figure 6. It consists of two sub committees and seven working groups.

¹² source: <https://www.iso.org/committee/656906.html>

¹³ source: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal11>

Figure 6. Overview of the structure of ISO/TC 268.

The standardization work of subcommittee ISO/TC 268/SC 1 *Smart community infrastructures* whose secretariat is held by Japan includes basic concepts for defining and describing community infrastructure intelligence as an integrative, large-scale product, harmonized metrics for benchmarking, use of metrics for application to different types of communities, and specifications for measurement/reporting/verification. Emphasis is placed on the technical aspects of smart municipal infrastructure, i.e., the underlying structures that support the operations and activities of urban communities, e.g., energy, water, resource management systems, and ICT infrastructure. The concept of intelligence is addressed in terms of the performance of technologically feasible solutions, considering several aspects, including sustainability.¹⁴

The second subcommittee ISO/TC 268/SC 2 *Sustainable mobility and transportation* whose secretariat is also held by Japan and aims to promote as well as support a multi-sectorial integrated approach of sustainable cities and communities with a long-term vision. Further, organizational issues, infrastructures and services in the mobility and transportation options for cities and communities, including those related to new technologies (i.e. electric, hydrogen, autonomous) are considered. The standards developed in this subcommittee shall provide requirements, frameworks, guidance and supporting techniques and tools for cities and territories, as well as all mobility and transportation stakeholders to plan, develop, operate, maintain and manage sustainable mobility and transportation systems and services with a long-term vision.¹⁵

¹⁴ source: <https://www.iso.org/committee/656967.html>

¹⁵ source: <https://www.iso.org/committee/8742800.html>

The ISO/TC 268, in general, already published 32 standards, and 22 standards are now under development.¹⁶ For the PROBONO project these standards are important since they form the overall and general basis for all the work which will be done during the project lifetime. It is also important to know which standards are coming in the next few months to implement them in the development processes and be in accordance with them.

The flagship standard of ISO/TC 268 is, as ISO promotes on their website, *ISO 37101: Sustainable development in communities – Management system for sustainable development – Requirements with guidance for use*.¹⁷ It is aimed at city leaders and shall provide an overall framework of what a sustainable community is and how to achieve one. This standard presents a guideline on what a city must address to become smarter, such as responsible resource use, environmental management, citizens' health and well-being, governance, mobility and more. This standard is supported by a number of different standards in areas such as terminology and key indicators for measuring the performance of city services including *ISO 37100: Sustainable cities and communities – Vocabulary*, *ISO 37105: Sustainable cities and communities – Descriptive framework for cities and communities* and *ISO 37120: Sustainable cities and communities – Indicators for city services and quality of life*.¹⁸

The equivalent to ISO/TC 268 on European level is CEN/TC 465 *Sustainable Cities and Communities* which secretariat is also held by AFNOR (France).¹⁹ The scope and the orientation of work of this TC is the same as the one from ISO/TC 268. CEN/TC 465 was established in 2020²⁰ which is why no standards have been published by this TC yet.

Furthermore, at European level the Sector Forum Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities (SF-SSCC) which is a strategic structure between CEN-CENELEC and ETSI is of importance. This joint group was created in January 2017 and acts as an advisory and coordinating body for European standardization activities in the field of smart and sustainable cities and communities but will not develop its own standards.²¹

¹⁶ source: <https://www.iso.org/committee/656906/x/catalogue/p/1/u/0/w/0/d/0>

¹⁷ source: <https://www.iso.org/sdg/SDG11.html>

¹⁸ source: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100423.pdf>

¹⁹ source:

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2691595&cs=1B4B2B4D071921D6418AE8D855A9F8585

²⁰ source: <https://standards.cencenelec.eu/BPCEN/2691595.pdf>

²¹ source: <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/smart-cities>

To get an impression of which other TCs could be important in the context of PROBONO besides the ones focusing explicitly on sustainable cities and communities, the brochure “ISO and sustainable cities” provides an overview.¹⁸ In Figure 7, an outline of the TC that are important in the context of sustainability and cities from the brochure is shown.

Figure 7. Overview of the TC's on an international level, which are important in the context of sustainability and cities¹⁸

As already mentioned at the beginning of this section and which is now noticeable from Figure 6, there is a variety of areas that must be considered when talking about sustainable cities. Regarding the PROBONO project Figure 7 illustrates the importance of focusing on specific areas which are of high relevance for the work in PROBONO regarding standardization. The overall topic of sustainable cities, which also includes GBN, is strongly connected to topics like energy management systems, responsible water consumption, infrastructure, security and resilience, connectivity, as well as health and well-being, to just name a few. Therefore, as also already described in the beginning, it must be figured out with the help of all the PROBONO partners in which specific areas it is necessary to provide a deeper insight into standardization to use these standards as a basis for developing and/or implementing innovations in the PROBONO context.

3 GBN analysis tools and DSS context and background

This chapter presents context and background information on GBN analysis tools and DSS in terms of human-focused simulation and analysis, GBN Maturity Assessment, climate adaptation and resilience tool, and biodiversity options analysis associated with the subtasks defined in PROBONO task T1.1.

3.1 Simulation and analysis tools in the AECO sector

In the last two decades, simulation and analysis tools made a substantial contribution to the significant progress in the development of high-performance buildings and neighbourhoods. Sustainable design, performance-based design, and low-carbon design are all requirements used to describe an intention to integrate current simulation and analysis tools and decision support systems in the AECO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operation) sector. Realities such as rapid urbanization, urban densification, and an exponential rise in computing power are transforming the way we design, construct and use buildings and cities.

In this perspective, the application of strong decision support and simulation tools and methods can be the most trustworthy way to make design decisions, e.g., testing how buildings or the elements of buildings will perform under real-world conditions. This is done using a mathematical model that re-creates conditions in a virtual environment. These computer-based analyses and simulations enable architects and engineers (the design team) to evaluate the performance of their proposed solutions, which are relevant to the design, construction, operation, and control of buildings (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Building industry infrastructure (source: [27] based on[28])

Users provide information like building geometry, location, climate data, lighting requirements, occupancy profiles, etc. Based on these inputs, analysis and simulation results determine energy use intensity, thermal comfort, indoor air quality, CO2 levels, life cycle cost, etc. Current major use categories of analysis-based and simulation-based tools in the AECO sector, based on [29], include:

- *Architectural Design*: quantitatively compare design or retrofit options to inform a more energy-efficient building design
- *HVAC Design*: calculate thermal loads for sizing of mechanical equipment and help design and test system control strategies
- *Building Performance Rating*: demonstrate performance-based compliance with energy codes, green certification, and financial incentives
- *Building Stock Analysis*: support the development of energy codes and standards and plan large scale energy efficiency programs
- *CFD in buildings*: simulation of boundary conditions like surface heat fluxes and surface temperatures for a following CFD study of the situation

A general framework, based on [30], for performance-based simulation software, classifies tools as follows:

- Applications with an integrated simulation engine (e.g. EnergyPlus, ESP-r, IES-VE, IDA ICE)
- Software that docks to a certain engine (e.g. Designbuilder, eQuest, RIUSKA, Sefaira)
- Plugins for other software enabling certain performance analyses (e.g. DIVA for Rhino, Honeybee, Autodesk Green Building Studio)

While building design is traditionally regarded as “the art and science of building,” building design education around the world is still seeking a balanced curriculum that provides a firm foundation in both the qualitative (aesthetic, visual, social, etc.) and quantitative (energy consumption, thermal comfort, indoor air quality, CO2 emissions, etc.) elements of design creativity. The sustainability movement has yielded new and widely recognized building performance standards that are leading building developers to demand design teams to achieve such standards to remain competitive in the real estate market.

In this view, building simulation and analysis tools can be developed and applied to allow us to simplify the complexity of sustainability-focused decision-making on building design aspects, especially as they become ‘smarter’ and more inextricably linked to a digital asset like a digital twin. Despite a steady drive to adopt sound environmental design principles, designers must still

work hard for buildings to remain comfortable, safe, and more liveable for occupants. Modelling and simulation allow building professionals to iterate designs, select materials and equipment, and ensure that tough decisions are made to meet the needs of a building when it is in use [27]. Likewise, sufficient building simulations can help balance energy efficiency with occupant comfort while reducing costs and time in the design process. Embracing Building Information Modelling (BIM) [31] has been a valuable step in this transformation journey. By using BIM methods and standards to create digital representations of assets collaboratively, organizations have achieved new levels of consistency and efficiency in design, construction, and operations [32].

Current BIM development work tends to be focused on the design and construction phases (and with minimal interoperability for integrative performance simulation support) but has not yet extended to consider ongoing performance monitoring and diagnostics throughout the life cycle of the building [27]. Particularly for complex buildings, effective operations have significant impacts on ensuring that the predicted design performance is actually achieved and sustained throughout the building life cycle. Therefore, a comprehensive dynamic life cycle building information model for the “total building performance and diagnostics” approach is needed to address the entire building delivery process and ongoing commissioning of high-performance buildings. According to [27],

“the model structure can be based on the Industry Foundation Class (IFC) schema (as endorsed by NBIMS) that will capture (a) “static” building information generated during the design and construction process and shared among the design architects and engineers particularly to support building performance predictions using various building simulation tools, benchmark evaluations (e.g., DGNB), and advanced design optimizations; (b) “dynamic” (operational) building information generated from large-scale occupancy detection and environmental sensing network for ongoing commissioning, whole building performance monitoring, and advanced adaptive controls based on occupant behavioural studies.”

This integrated model will also serve as a rich repository of comprehensive, evidence-based case studies for ongoing research and development as well as education of professionals for the building industry in the long term. While most analysis and simulation tools and methods focus on testing structural, energy-related, and acoustics performances, *human-centric simulation and analysis tools* that e.g. simulate human visual perception and cognition are relatively new and thus provide a fertile ground for research and discussion. This includes the space syntax

suite of methodologies and analysis tools [33] and other static analysis (i.e., non-simulation) tools [34, 35], agent-based modelling and simulation for analysing egress, wayfinding and so on [36, 37], and spatial artefact theory for modelling and reasoning about human experience and behaviour [38-40]

3.1.1 Human centred design framework based on social sustainability factors

Stated objective from GA (Grant agreement): Human-focused simulation and analysis for decision support through planning and (early) design of new and renovation of buildings as specified in 1.3.1.1.

Human-centred qualities in the built environment are the main contributors to social sustainability. Social sustainability is the weakest defined pillar of sustainability, that has been emerged through continuous iterations over time [41]. Through our recent work in [42], we presented that social sustainability is a term that spans concepts such as the fulfilment of basic needs, the sense of community, quality of life, justice, equity, equality, security, health, well-being, etc. These concepts are getting regulated and measured on vastly different levels, from the national and international goals presented in the UN's agenda for sustainable development [43], to a building or individual level as done in building certification systems (Including the Danish DGNB [19], WELL [44], BREEAM [17] and LEED [16]). The consequence of this broad definition is that, if social sustainability is not further defined, the concept will act as an empty conceptual space with no clear meaning and weight [42, 45]. Due to this, we introduce the concept of social values in Kristoffersen et. al. [42]. This way, the focus is on the added values of selected aspects and interventions, thereby making it clear that the overarching social sustainability is not assessed or evaluated.

Building upon our work in Kristoffersen [46], social values can be divided into actions and impacts at three different levels. As presented in Figure 9, these three levels are as follows:

- **Global and governmental:** Concepts about social values that are regulated and measured on a global scale. Examples of this level of social values are working conditions, terms of employment, equality of rights and the UN sustainable development goals [43].
- **City and neighbourhood:** This level of social values is focussed on the impacts and assessments in the communities and neighbourhoods in which humans are either located or active. Concepts included in this level of social values include the

minimization of crimes, the accessibility of infrastructure, equality, and the forming of local communities.

- **Human-centred:** The level of social values that is focussed on how humans feel and perceive their surroundings on the scale of the individual person. This includes terms such as thermal and visual comfort, as well as the direct short- and long-term impact on humans' health by the environment directly around people.

Figure 9. Illustration of the three levels of social values.

The literature has shown the way building certification systems are approaching social sustainability based on social values [42]. The values and aspects assessed in the building certification systems (e.g. thermal comfort, daylight, acoustics etc.) are also being described using terms such as comfort, indoor environmental quality, comfort, and well-being [45-50]. A comparison between the certification systems DGNB Denmark, the WELL building standard, BREEAM international and LEED, and has shown that the social values addressed in these certification systems have large overlaps when compared to the level of the values, with the large difference between the certification systems assessment of social qualities being based on the different traditions, and regulations that the certification systems are based on [46].

The values assessed in the certification systems are all focussing on the human perspective and the scale of individual humans, this is in line with the definition of human-centred design presented in ISO 9241-210:2019:

“Human-centred design is an approach to interactive systems development that aims to make systems usable and useful by focussing on the users, their needs and requirements, and by

applying human factors/ergonomics, and usability knowledge and techniques. This approach enhances effectiveness and efficiency, improves human well-being, user satisfaction, accessibility and sustainability; and counteracts possible adverse effects of use on human” [51]

This quote highlights that human-centred design is focused on many of the same concepts as social values when addressed on a building level. An existing challenge in this regard is that these social values are introduced into a building project in the design and planning stages. During these stages, the involved stakeholders change, which poses the risk of the intention and argument for the social values getting lost and forgotten through the process [52, 53], as the stakeholders' viewpoints and argumentation have not been explicitly incorporated into the project. To combat this, we propose a human-centred design framework [52, 53], which can be used to capture and formalize the socially oriented design intentions through the design stages to ensure that the socially oriented intentions do not get lost when stakeholders change. Using the framework will, therefore, ensure that the socially oriented design intention will be present in the final building as a social value the building users will experience.

3.1.2 Workflow for capturing and formalizing socially oriented design intentions

For capturing and formalization of socially oriented design intentions, we have developed the ProFormalize framework [52, 53]. The framework consists of four stages: elicitation, organisation, formalisation, and implementation. The following description of the framework is based on our work in [53].

The elicitation stage represents the capturing of the design arguments regarding socially-oriented values from experts in the field. In the organisation stage, arguments are sorted out as items of social intentions and their corresponding design activities. The formalization stage translates the output of the organization stage into first-order logic formulas to be outputted to the final stage, which is the software implementation. The overall workflow of the framework is illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. The overall workflow of ProFormalize, showing its four stages; elicitation, organization, formalization and implementation.

Stage 1 – Elicitation

The elicitation of social intents and corresponding design activities is performed through semi-structured interviews with the practising architect and the transcription of the interview recording. The outcome of this stage creates the initial database that contains all the design arguments that the architect mentioned during the interview. This database contains the architectural design activities that have been implemented and that have been show during the interview, as well as their corresponding socially-oriented intentions.

Stage 2 – Organization

The organisation stage consists of identifying social intents and design activities in the transcription and adding the social intents and design activities to the organized database. Each intent is added as a row in the table containing information about the social intent, design activity, the interview in which the intent is mentioned, interview timestamp, which building the intent is present in, and an excerpt from the transcription describing the intent in the words of the interviewee.

Stage 3 – Formalization

The formalization stage of architectural arguments is the stage when these arguments are explicitly represented, that is, systematically identifying ambiguous and implicit aspects of each argument and deciding how to make them clear and explicit. This includes the sensory experience of building occupants and the conditions of their surrounding environment, in addition to qualitative spatial prepositions that should be connected to clear and straightforward definitions.

Stage 4 – Implementation

The implementation of the formalized architectural arguments as Abstract Syntax Trees (AST). In a direct one-to-one translation process, first order logic formulas are transformed into abstract syntax trees to be prepared for software implementation. Within the abstract syntax trees, the following elements are defined: (1) **logical expressions**, which are statements that evaluate to either *true* or *false*, and this includes logical operators (*and*, *or*, *not*), and predicates (*Pred*), (2) **terms**, which includes functions that are applied to terms and they result in a new term, and variables that represent different terms. Figure 11 shows an example of an abstract syntax tree representation.

```
And(Pred("occupant", 1, [Var("P")]),
  And(Pred("buildingElement", 1, [Var("A")]),
    Pred("inside", 2, [Var("P"), Func("visibleSpace", 1, [Var("A")])])
  ))
```

Figure 11. Example of an abstract syntax tree representation, showing a logical operator (AND), predicates (*occupant*, *buildingElement*, *inside*), a function (*visibleSpace*) and variables (*A*, *P*). *Occupant (P)* must be inside the visible space of the building element (*A*)

3.2 GBN Maturity Assessment

Stated objective from GA (Grant agreement): Provide a GBN Maturity Index tool for GBN initiators to establish a ‘greening benchmarking position’ and identify technology greening measures against prevailing regulations and financial realities to determine and set realistic GBN targets for the short, medium, and long long-term (2025, 2030, 2050).

GBNs need support to strategize and map progress on their journey and better understand the transformation ahead. These steps need to be mapped to the concept of Green Building Neighbourhoods to assess their progress and relative maturity against what PROBONO defines as a model GBN, adjusted to the vision, specificities and constraints of each place. The maturity assessment can therefore be considered as a tool for all GBN stakeholders to assess their GBN, and provide an initial benchmark informing downstream discussions. This audit allows GBNs to understand their position on the journey at a given point in time, and to identify the next steps to strategically achieve both their “business as usual” objectives as well as PROBONO’s. Similarly to an HR “360” approach, engaging the different GBN stakeholders would yield a holistic vision of a GBN and provide insights on many areas that a single interviewee could not cover by themselves.

3.2.1 Overall approach

State-of-the-art maturity assessments usually work in a discrete number of categories, usually between 4 and 6. The levels gradually cover the range from a “business as usual” to a “leading” status, which the GBNs would aim to follow to become best in class. It is noted that the assessment needs to target specific GBN stakeholders – however, it could be interesting to propose the assessment to non-responsible stakeholders to assess the “perceived level of maturity” of a GBN.

The particularity of the PROBONO subject is that the GBNs do follow a lifecycle for which maturities can change. In essence, the phases can follow the “Design, Build, Operate” framework. As such, greenfield and brownfield differences can be integrated into this framework. The end-of-life considerations need to be integrated into the “Design” phase of the project.

In line with modern common practices, the assessment will need to be undertaken online to allow easy-to-contact interaction with the target GBN. One of our partners, Mott MacDonald, has already developed similar tools, such as the Smart Infrastructure Index, which aims to measure digital maturity. A similar approach could be undertaken.

By proposing this assessment to the wider GBN communities and different stakeholders, PROBONO could enhance its knowledge base with more information from other GBNs and promote the identification and mobilization of more GBNs to leverage PROBONO's reach.

3.2.2 Building on international, recognized standards

Following the first years of the project, we do propose an updated approach, simplifying the initial approach while maintaining the breadth of coverage of the assessment. We plan on adapting our approach to the ISO/TS 37107:2019(E) standard, which provides guidelines for assessing the maturity of a community's sustainability performance. It includes a maturity model called the Maturity Model for Sustainable and Smart Communities (MMSSC), which consists of five levels of maturity for the different dimensions of a GBN, such as smart enablers, citizen-centricity, open collaboration, and progress towards sustainability purposes.

As a baseline, PROBONO can use the ISO 37100 series (Sustainable Cities and Communities) as the standard covers both cities and neighbourhoods (or communities) on a scale. It can also benefit from the maturity assessment from ISO 37107, which *“provides a top-level maturity model for smart, sustainable communities (MMSSC), which can be used for self-assessment by*

individual cities and communities and as the basis for cross-city benchmarking. The MMSSC is a simple way for community leaders to assess how mature their community is in its journey towards adoption of good practices as set out in ISO standards for sustainable and smart-enabled development; to identify strengths and weaknesses; and then to quickly find their way to the international standards and guidance that are most relevant to their needs.”.

The Maturity Assessment can be used by GBNs to drive improved performance and continuous improvement. It can be integrated into the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle for sustainability management, where other documents in the series (such as ISO 37104) provide detailed guidance on implementing the PDCA cycle in the context of ISO 37101 management system for sustainable communities. The Maturity Assessment will be used at each stage of the PDCA cycle, including commitment, baseline review, strategy definition, action plan implementation, and performance evaluation and continuous improvement. This is a focus on a GBN maturity assessment but does not go into more specific maturity assessments, for example, about GBN "smart infrastructure maturity assessment", covered in ISO 37153.

Figure 12. Overview of the ISO37107 MMMSSC structure

An ISO 37101 methodology has been used in practical implementation, for example, in the case of French housing assessing green neighbourhoods²².

This approach particularly matches with PROBONO’s vision of supporting GBNs, and matches with the following characteristics: *User-focused* (developed with/for GBN and community leaders to ensure it meets their needs in a user-friendly way), *Comprehensive* (covers key GBN-wide challenges involved in the journey to become a sustainable and smart-enabled), *Applicable*

²² 190404_monographie_iso_presqu_ile_en.pdf (logement.gouv.fr)

to all communities (useful for GBNs of any scale, both urban and rural), *Simple to use* (intuitively easy to use - should not require extensive and costly data collection), *Flexible* (applicable to very different sizes and types of community, regardless of their social, economic, and cultural context), *Technology-neutral* (not assessed against specific technologies or solutions, which risk rapidly becoming outdated), *Action-oriented* (designed so that any gaps or weaknesses it identifies can easily be matched against practical advice within international standards on how a community can address these), and *Extensible/interoperable* (flexible evolution and use).

3.2.3 Review of maturity of a GBN organization and a GBN programme

The proposed approach above allows for the mapping of two aspects of a GBN:

- **GBN organization:** what maturity does the GBN demonstrate in terms of its organisation and delivery capacity and capability?
- **GBN delivery:** is the programme of activities clear, aligned with a GBN vision, and does it cover the possible issues and concerns of the GBN framework inspired from ISO37100 standards?

We review these two points below.

3.2.3.1 Review of the GBN programme maturity

3.2.3.1.1 Objective

The objective of this review is to help identify how the “GBN Vision” and the “GBN Programme of activities” can be projected on the 6x12 matrix proposed by the standard. We also include the aspect of scale, be it neighbourhood or building. The end result can be summarized as, in the case of the preliminary review for Aarhus seen in Figure 13

Figure 13. Comparing AAR UC (circles) to vision (stars). Size corresponds to the relative importance on an likert scale.

The “stars” capture the vision of the LL, and the circles the activities within the programme.

3.2.3.1.2 Formalizing the vision of the LL

For the sake of this assessment, we designed a Python, LLM-based tool that uses text inputs from the Living Labs (D7.2: GBN Visions) to draft an assessment of the vision (the “stars” above), which is then reviewed by a LL representative, and firmed up.

The same process is used for activities.

The process uses Excel files as described in Figure 14

Figure 14. Picture of the Excel file used to formalize the vision for the LL.

3.2.3.1.3 Output of the review

The vision and programme alignment are created back, taking into consideration pre-assessment and human reviews. This allows discussions of GBN leaders, such as “Is this a fair representation of our LL vision?” “Is this a fair representation of our projects?” “Is this a fair representation of our ambitions?” or “Are our ambitions supported by activities?”

The output of these exchanges can be used to refine and steer the development of the GBN Programme, iteratively.

3.2.3.2 Review of the GBN organisation maturity

3.2.3.2.1 Level 1 breakdown

The main categories of the MMGBN (Maturity Model for GBNs) are as follows:

- **Purposes:** GBN's maturity in achieving the six purposes of a sustainable community, as defined in ISO 37101.
- **Strategy Management:** GBN's maturity in establishing and implementing a smart city operating model, using smart technologies, data, and ways of working.
- **Citizen-Centric Service Management:** GBN's maturity in providing citizen-centric services and engaging citizens in decision-making processes.
- **Digital and Physical Resource Management:** GBN's maturity in managing digital and physical resources efficiently and sustainably.

Table 4 proposes a preliminary assessment matrix

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
	Initial	Partially fulfilled	Fulfilled	Improving	Sustainably optimizing
Purposes	Processes to manage the GBN enablers or purposes either do not exist or are managed on a fragmented basis. There is no strategy or consistent framework in place, and actions are ad hoc and fragmented.	Some progress is being made towards a GBN-wide plan, but it is not consistently applied. Some processes have been established to consult interested parties, but they are ad hoc. Community leaders have identified priorities and developed a community-wide plan.	The GBN has established GBN-wide management processes and communication and engagement processes. GBN communities leaders have baselined current performance, established success criteria and trajectories, and established accountability and governance structures.	The GBN can demonstrate that it is measuring the performance of processes and achieving positive impacts. Interested parties are engaged in governance, and there is evidence of performance improvement. Communities and authority buy-in is substantial.	This level builds upon the previous levels and includes continuous improvement and optimization. There is evidence of ongoing evaluation, learning, and feedback. Digital dashboards provide real-time insight, and policies are evaluated for effectiveness.
Strategy Management					
Citizen-Centric Service Management					
Digital and Physical Resource Management					

Table 4. The proposed matrix concept, based on ISO37107

3.2.3.2.2 Level 2 breakdown

For each of the 4 overarching dimensions of a GBN, the maturity assessment can delve a level lower, following the sub-dimensions in Table 5.

Strategy Management	Citizen centric service management	Digital & Physical resources management	Purposes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GBN Vision • Leadership and Governance • Collaborative engagement • Procurement and supplier management • Benefit realization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivering integrated citizen centric services • Empowering the GBN communities through GBN data • Channels and access • Privacy and Security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing smart GBN development and infrastructure • Managing IT and Data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractiveness • Well-being • Preservation and improvement of environment • Social Cohesion • Responsible resource use • Resilience

Table 5. The sub-dimensions of the overarching dimensions of a GBN.

These dimensions are further split into “characteristics” that are assessed in the questionnaire.

3.2.4 Use of certifications, standards, .. with this assessment

The different schemes presented earlier, including but not limited to BREEAM, LEED, RE2020, DGNB, CEEQUAL, ... can be used as a means for the GBN community to demonstrate maturity, but are not an answer per se.

3.2.5 Results

The outputs of the activity, as well as possible next steps for this task within PROBONO, are presented below.

Learning: The assessment will benefit from a visual output, helping the GBN understand at a glance their progress – taking for example the form of a radar-map (see Figure 15), built from a consolidation of the results. This radar map could be complemented by possible “low hanging fruits” or opportunity a GBN could take.

Figure 15. Example of an assessment mapping output²³

A call for action: As more assessment is done, the exercise could enable benchmarking of GBNs' performances and linking pathways to tried-out approaches and measures demonstrated in practice by GBNs, allowing the interviewee to build confidence in implementing these measures.

²³ source: 190404_monographie_iso_presqu_ile_en.pdf (logement.gouv.fr)

3.3 GBN climate adaptation and resilience

Stated objective from GA (Grant agreement): Support climate change impacts and risks and specify mitigation and adaptation options considering territorial diagnostics, weather and climate data services predictive monitoring, and technology options.

When considering climatic adaptation and resilience of buildings, one must first define appropriate metrics for identifying risks and assessing sensitivity and vulnerability. It is very important to define indicators based on an international standard that can be considered as “common grounds” between the implicated sites. In the same logic, once projections are to be made, these should be based on clear trajectories and well-defined scenarios. Therefore, the future evolution of the selected indicators will be modelled using IPCC scenarios.

Accordingly, the following scenarios will be used:

- a) The SSP 2-4.5 IPCC scenario that predicts a radiative forcing of 4.5W/m^2 and the persistence of current socio-economic pathways.
- b) The SSP 5-8.5 IPCC scenario, which predicts a radiative forcing of 8.5W/m^2 with an increasing fossil-fuelled development.

Using these scenarios, the years 2050 and 2070 will be used as projection horizons for the selected indicators. The year 2050 was chosen since it is considered a milestone of the EU green vision, while 2070 mostly represented the end year of a 2020-built building. Below is the list of indicators chosen for adapting green buildings to climate change.

- Air quality: concentration of particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5), NO2, and O3 in ambient air

Air quality is a key factor for inhabitants of a green building. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), reducing the air pollution can help reduce diseases including asthma, lung cancer, heart disease.

Residents of all the LLs are concerned by air quality. It can have minor or major impacts on their health (particularly for the most vulnerable groups). This indicator should be considered a metric for comparing with air quality guidelines established by the WHO and the European Commission.

- Heatwaves

According to the IPCC (2014, 2019) heat waves will become longer, more frequent and more extreme. This can cause severe dehydration and respiratory distress (among other negative health effects). Most populations at risk are children, elders, and people with chronic diseases.

Heatwaves can induce a significant increase in energy consumption. For example, the extended use of air conditioning significantly increases electrical consumption.

Adaptation to heat waves is key to establishing an energy-efficient building and providing comfort to the inhabitants of the concerned Living Labs.

- Marine submersion

Marine submersion indicators are particularly relevant to the case of Aarhus, Porto, and Dublin. It is considered a high-priority challenge as through submersion and flooding, buildings and infrastructure can be significantly damaged or impaired.

- Strong winds: Number of days with wind speed greater than 90 km/h

Wind damage on buildings depends on the geographical setting, the morphology, and the envelope of the building. Additionally, high speed winds can make trees fall, hence damaging buildings and property. Antennas and roof equipment displacement or damages are also possible in such events. In the same manner, physical wind-induced damage to assets near electrical networks or other infrastructure can influence the latter's functioning.

- River flooding

Porto, Dublin, Madrid, Prague, Brussels and Aarhus are crossed by rivers. This setting makes these cities threatened by floods. Based on the predictions of this indicator, the design of green buildings can incorporate flooding resilience into its planning schemes. This inclusion can prevent flood-induced structural weakening.

- Clay swelling and shrinking

Depending on the soil, its proportion of clay minerals, and surface/underground hydrology, soil swelling and shrinking can occur. The shrink-swell process refers to the extent to which certain clay minerals expand when wet and retract when dry.

Climate change will significantly impact precipitations in Europe, and changes in soil shrink-swell capacities will surely follow. Coupled with subsidence or heaves, shrinks and swells can significantly affect the integrity of building foundations.

With heave and subsidence of the foundations and the infrastructure of the building can suffer damage.

- Freeze-Thaw

Freeze and thaw can impact buildings in different proportions, depending on their structure and the building material used. Water can fill cracks, and then freezing can enlarge cracks, leading to substantial damage with time.

Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature (TNn): °C

This indicator is interesting to study as its fluctuations can provide insights into the amount of energy required for heating or cooling systems. It is also an important factor in designing the insulation of energy-efficient buildings.

3.4 GBN biodiversity adaptation

Stated objective from GA (Grant agreement): Adapt the International Biodiversity & Property Council BiodiverCity® schemes in creating GBN environments, which accommodate various living nature spaces.

3.4.1 Why must city and real estate stakeholders consider biodiversity?

Biodiversity is one of today's major issues, gathering all sustainable development areas - energy, health, mobility, and resources management. In practice, urban biodiversity measures our daily contact with the natural world. Biodiversity in the city should be visible and mean something to everyone, not only regarding green spaces and gardens, but in "bio-architecture" such as green walls and green roofs. All stakeholders involved in design and construction, from single buildings to district-scale, need to share a common vision regarding the principal issues for integrating biodiversity into the built environment:

- First, the erosion of biodiversity, upon which Humanity is dependent, is a global crisis that needs to be addressed with speed. Cities can play a vital role in accelerating the greening of urban environments to create "garden cities" that mitigate climate change effects.
- Second, if demographic projections are correct, some 80% of the world's population will be urban by 2050, putting huge pressures on resources of clean air, water, and liveable spaces. To address this challenge, cities will need to integrate a maximum number of green spaces (large, canopied street trees, parcs, flower gardens, vegetation in courtyards, in front of buildings, on rooftops, etc.), as well as the essential biodiversity that supports these green spaces: birds, squirrels, insects, earth worms, soil bacteria, etc.
- Connection with Nature, even on small scales, helps to achieve "experiences of nature", which is a real lever to engage people, individually and collectively, to protect biodiversity.

- Urban biodiversity in all its forms – fauna, flora, water, soil – delivers:
 - Ecological benefits – preserving and fostering ‘blue’ (small waterways, ponds, and rivers) and ‘green’ (flowers, trees, gardens, parks, woods) living frameworks.
 - Environmental benefits – improving soil permeability, water infiltration, greater O2 delivery / CO2 absorption, shade, mitigation of urban heat island effects, etc.
 - Economic benefits – improving the attractiveness of cities will increase desirability for city-dwellers, attract talented job-seekers, increase the value of real estate, and maximize the best conditions promoting commercial investment in workspaces, jobs, industrial plants, R&D centres, logistics operations, etc.
 - Health, social and societal benefits – a healthier natural environment enhances well-being, health, hospitality, sharing, and the sense of belonging.

- The demand for a greater presence of Nature in the city is clear: 9 out of 10 people in Europe consider the vicinity of green spaces to be an essential part of their life-balance. It is even a factor of attractiveness for companies: 83% of young graduates want to work in green offices. ‘Biophilia’ is the new concept that formalises this need for Nature.

The urban planning and real estate sectors are undertaking significant innovations in the construction and renovation of sustainable buildings and neighbourhoods, with a view to develop greener, more resilient, and more socially integrated cities. So far, biodiversity has not been a top priority, however it is a major and meaningful issue related to climate change, the greening of neighbourhoods, and the well-being of city dwellers. Ecological amenities, biophilic architecture, gardens, and green terraces are valuable assets of property attractiveness.

Because climate and biodiversity are intimately linked, biodiversity must become a priority within the environmental planning and actions of city stakeholders.

3.4.2 General IBPC’s contribution to PROBONO

IBPC is to provide support on work packages 2, 3, 7, 8 and 9.

IBPC brings added value to GBN principles by adding a strong urban biodiversity approach to the PROBONO living labs.

IBPC’s BiodiverCity® certification tools and guidelines will be used, *without following the certification process*, with the following targets:

- to enhance urban biodiversity on public and private areas and evaluate the grow of the "ecological potential" (our main KPI).

- to develop nature-based solutions.
- to develop biophilic amenities for the city dwellers.
- to organise and develop the relationship between citizens and nature.

BiodiverCity® certification's tools provide a streamlined approach for the benefit of stakeholders in the sustainable urban planning and real estate sector, helping them to measure and display the progress they make while integrating biodiversity into their new or refurbishing investment projects as well in the day-to-day life of their existing properties and neighbourhoods. BiodiverCity® is an innovative package of tools which sets tangible standards in the rather complex field of biodiversity in the city. It emphasizes the improvements that must be made and sets a relationship of mutual trust between stakeholders: project owners, city dwellers, and their partners.

The BiodiverCity® certification process is not the target of the PROBONO project. The target is to develop a strong and professional biodiversity approach within urban planning and real estate development and management as a set of best practices.

Deliverables should also include an evaluation through the stated KPIs at the start of the project (initial stand), and after 4 years.

3.4.3 Concepts and targets

Biodiversity expresses the diversity of life forms (animal, insect, microbial, and horticultural species) within our environment. The term also applies to the complexity of spontaneous interactions, chemical exchanges, natural dynamics, and organization levels of living systems, from ecosystems, to species, to genes. These elements interact synergistically and stabilize over long time-frames, and according to local contexts.

Urban biodiversity is made up of flora and fauna present in the biological habitat of the city (trees, lawns, flowers, soils) inside public and private spaces (parcs, gardens, patios, courtyards, roofs, parking lots, lawns, roofs, terraces, flower boxes, balconies, etc.) Biodiversity also designates the whole range of benefits derived from itself, as biodiversity is its own reward.

The concept of biodiversity includes both the wild and spontaneous elements of nature and planted ones (gardens). In the city, life is dependent on climatic disturbances: mineral substrates, disturbed soils, microclimates, pollution, etc.

We reckon that an ecosystem is made of a biotope (the physio-chemical environment) and the biocenosis (living organisms, flora, fauna...), the latter being spontaneous. The construction of

new buildings generates new biotopes that are more-or-less compatible with the biocenosis that is already present, and this can present problems to biodiversity.

The science of biodiversity is called scientific ecology. The scientific specialists are called ecologists.

The purpose of Ecological Engineering is to implement green systems (ecosystems, vegetal dynamics, plant biology, pedogenesis, animal populations...) that will be self-sustaining, even if originally man-made.

The maintenance of gardens, the regulation of animal species, etc. is called Ecological management. The goals set by implementing biodiversity in the built environment are negotiated and decided among the stakeholders. The biodiversity aspects of a project include the notion of global cost: the “greening” of a project has an operational cost and a maintenance cost. Therefore, the BiodiverCity® label also integrates Facilities Management in and around the buildings. The approach allows the flexible management of the landscaped areas according to their specificity and their function, as not all areas require the same kind of maintenance and care.

3.4.4 WP7 – Living Lab implementation and scoping - suggested approach

- IBPC's three BiodiverCity® labels offers an innovative package of tools for a new generation of “GREEN BUILDINGS” AND “GREEN NEIGHBOURHOODS”. The tools first explain the context and develop the concept of urban biodiversity and detail the technical grid helping to conduct biodiversity improvement on investment projects or existing buildings and neighbourhoods. The tools are intended for users of the reference data and all persons willing to learn more about the approach. The tools present the objectives and topics to be achieved. Technical criteria for the evaluation are described in technical manuals, which detail the actions to be conducted to achieve a level of biodiversity that can then be certified by one of the three BiodiverCity® labels.

Beyond the simple design of greening with vegetation, these tools introduce a new approach to the ecological functions of green spaces as well as new dimensions to maintaining landscapes and buildings together.

The methodology is backed by a package of technical guides designed for the City policy makers and real estate stakeholders such as planners, investors, architects, developers, and property managers. The purpose is to match buildings and neighbourhoods with nature, vegetation, and quality of life using one of three complementary tools:

- **BiodiverCity® Construction** – for construction or renovation of any type of building project.
- **BiodiverCity® Ready** - for biodiversity and urban planning for new district development.
- **BiodiverCity® Life** - for existing properties or neighbourhoods.

Each of these certification standards includes:

- An explanatory guide.
- A technical manual.
- An assessment software (an exhaustive, analytical grid).

All these documents contain:

- A precise description of the criteria to target, and the procedures to classify the project or site according to the criteria;
- The type and format of information to gather and detail to justify the scoring level allocated by the criteria;
- A description of the assessment methods used to grant the performance level;
- A grid for the ecologist assessor for steering the procedure.

The tools are flexible and multipurpose (checklist, performance charts, progress reports), and define the rules governing the biodiversity performance tag for the project or site.

- *WORKING ON THE LIVING LAB* - The Four dimensions of performance for urban biodiversity projects: given the complexity of the subject and the variety of sites and projects, biodiversity cannot be assessed along one single axis or one single point of view. Our standards assemble the topics and data along 4 axes setting the conditions for success of any biodiversity project.

The four dimensions target different players and reflect different points of view:

1. *Commitment*: Project management and environmental aspects of the project.
2. *Project*: Architect, urban planner, designer, biodiversity, and layout of the project.
3. *Ecological potential*: Ecologist, nature-based and scientific indicators.
4. *Amenities*: User and city dweller, well-being, and services rendered by improved biodiversity.

4 Analysis tools and DSS tailored for PROBONO LLs

This chapter presents the *relevance*, *impact*, and *assessment* of the subtasks defined in PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for PROBONO LLs, including:

- Human-focused simulation and analysis tailored for PROBONO living labs,
- GBN maturity assessment tailored for PROBONO living labs,
- Climate adaptation and resilience tailored for PROBONO living labs, and
- Biodiversity adaptation tailored for PROBONO living labs

In this framework, the terms addressed are as follows:

- **Relevance:** how relevant is the topic to the LL, and in what way? Specify the particular aspects of the buildings and neighbourhoods in the LL where the topic can be applied.
- **Impact:** what are the benefits, advantages, or consequences of applying the topic to the LLs?
- **Assessment** of current tools, methods, or methodologies: how do you assess the capability of the existing methods, tools, or framework concerning the application of the topic for the LL?

The short descriptions of the LLs and the outline of the subtasks below are provided based on deliverable D7.1 report.

4.1 LL 1 – Dublin

The LL is located in Dún Laoghaire, in the south-eastern part of Dublin, close to the arrival point of the cross-channel ferries from Wales. Dún Laoghaire, as an area, is undergoing a transformation that influences the use of and business types in the area, as well as the general town design.

The LL will be focussed on a district level by engaging with the local citizens in the design and development of a green town centre and living neighbourhood, while also focussing on the retrofitting/renovation of the buildings presented in Table 6, which is located within the neighbourhood.

Building name	Building use	Year of construction	Net floor area (m ²)	Heated floor area (m ²)	Occupant capacity	Possibility for BIPV integration (Y/N)
County Hall	Local Government head office	1879; 1996	15528	15528	500	Y
Ferry Terminal	Currently vacant with new uses under consideration	1995	6580	6580	Vacant	Y
Lexicon Library	Public library	2015	8007	8007	Varies	Y
Harbour Master's Building	Office for DLR staff	1820	410	410	Approx. 30	Y
Social Housing	Residential	-	-	-	-	-

Table 6. Characteristics of the buildings in Dublin LL

In the following, Table 7 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Dublin LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.
<i>Impact</i>	n/a
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.
<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders.
<i>Assessment</i>	Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	The LL has the vision of identifying strategies for retrofit in the context of the local climate.
<i>Impact</i>	The LL has the vision of identifying strategies for retrofit in the context of the local climate.
<i>Assessment</i>	The LL has the vision of identifying strategies for retrofit in the context of the local climate.
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation
<i>Relevance</i>	The biodiversity initiatives are based on Dún Laoghaire-Rathdown County Biodiversity Action Plan. The biodiversity adaption can be relevant in this

	context. Also, the Dublin LL has open public spaces around the Lexicon Library, the Peoples' Park, and the recently refurbished Dún Laoghaire Baths, which will contribute to the GBN open spaces and biodiversity. There is potential for Dún Laoghaire harbour to also further contribute to this.
<i>Impact</i>	The benefit of applying biodiversity adaptation could be that it can serve as a tool to ensure and document the fulfilment of the County Biodiversity Action Plan.
<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity Construction framework to: -Initial site biodiversity status by an ecologist -Accompany the project with an ecologist to make recommendations using the biodiversity framework to strengthen the preservation of biodiversity, introduce more nature and work on well-being of residents. A rating will be carried out on the four axes and on the objectives of the Biodiversity construction framework

Table 7. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Dublin LL

4.2 LL 2 – Madrid

The LL is located within Madrid New North, a public initiative by the Madrid city council that focuses on 300 hectares of land around the Chamartin Station. The LL focuses on a neighbourhood level, with a large focus on establishing a geothermal network within the LL. Furthermore, the LL will also focus on constructing two new buildings.

In the following, Table 8 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Madrid LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	This topic can be relevant to the LL, concerning the construction of the two new buildings. If any of the new buildings are intended to obtain building certifications, the human-focused simulation and analysis can document some of the “softer” building qualities.
<i>Impact</i>	This topic can be relevant to the LL, concerning the construction of the two new buildings. If any of the new buildings are intended to obtain building certifications, the human-focused simulation and analysis can document some of the “softer” building qualities.
<i>Assessment</i>	This topic can be relevant to the LL, concerning the construction of the two new buildings. If any of the new buildings are intended to obtain building certifications, the human-focused simulation and analysis can document some of the “softer” building qualities.
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	Madrid New North is registered to archive LEED Cities and Communities, and BREEAM ES. The certification in both systems aims to obtain the highest level of certification in both systems. Furthermore, Level(s) and DGNB will be used to document and illustrate the focus on resource efficiency through the entire lifecycle.

<i>Impact</i>	A benefit of using the GBN maturity assessment with the building and district certification systems can be that GBN maturity assessment can be used as a tool to simplify and communicate the results of the building certifications in both multifaceted and multifaceted project-relevant contexts. The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders.
<i>Assessment</i>	Current tools to perform a GBN maturity assessment are building certification systems (e.g. BREEAM, LEED, and DGNB). A weakness of the certification systems can be that they condense the result of the entire certification into a single result, which can make it difficult to assess which qualities and levels of qualities, are obtained through the certification. The opaqueness in the certification systems is further reinforced by the flexibility in the systems to select and deselect different criteria based on the wants of the person or team making the documentation for the building certification. Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.
<i>Impact</i>	n/a
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation
<i>Relevance</i>	MNN green infrastructure strategy aims to bring biodiversity from outside the city to the city. To integrate the DHC plant as a green infrastructure, it is being designed so that the surface of the roof will be naturalized.
<i>Impact</i>	The new green infrastructure will also enhance the neighbourhood nature experience, increasing the square meters per inhabitant in the surroundings of MNN from 16,5 to 17,6.
<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity Construction framework to: -Initial site biodiversity status by an ecologist -Accompany the project, with an ecologist to make recommendations using the biodiversity framework to strengthen the preservation of biodiversity, introduce more nature and work on well-being of residents.

Table 8. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Madrid LL

4.3 LL 3 – Porto

The LL is the headquarters of Sonae, also called Sonae Campus, which is located in Maia city, in the northern part of the Porto Metropolitan area. The LL is using a neighbourhood approach, focusing on the campus as a collected unit, to become a world-class example of climate positiveness while also focusing on next-generation options, including biodiversity and social innovations.

The campus contains two existing buildings which are either LEED Gold certified in 2010 (Sonae Maia Business Center) or LEED Platinum 2020 (Tech Hub).

In the following, Table 9 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Porto LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	The project has the KPI of Monitoring, controlling, AI/forecasting tools development, and study of consumer behaviour (Further described in D7.1 section 7.1.3)
<i>Impact</i>	In addition to the existing KPI can not only focus on matching the consumption profiles to the curves of renewable energy, but also include the aspect of the users and their comfort in monitoring, controlling, and forecasting. This can provide the opportunity to optimise the building's energy use, and the performance of the technical systems, based on both the renewable energy curves and the optimization of the building user's comfort. The aspects of human comfort which can be documented using human-focused simulation and analysis can include thermal comfort and change in air quality.
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.
<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders.
<i>Assessment</i>	Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	The focus on climate adaptation and resilience is further relevant since the LL is located in an area where extreme temperatures (temperatures above 40 °C) are becoming more common during summer. This can increase the building's need for cooling, resulting in increased energy consumption by the building.
<i>Impact</i>	The constraint of extreme temperatures is mentioned in D7.1 within section 7.3.7 "Risk and constraints". The inclusion of the topic of climate adaptation and resilience in the LL, can be a better understanding of the risk and constraints related to climatic changes, while also providing the possibility to improve the building's resilience towards extreme temperatures.
<i>Assessment</i>	A study of the climatic exposure of the LL based on the 8.5 scenario at the 2050 and 2070 horizons must be done to measure the climatic hazards for which the LL is the most vulnerable. Then, an analysis of the components of the GBN must be done taking into account the sensitivity of the components to a hazard and its strategic importance on the good functionality of the GBN. This analysis of the components allows to obtain the vulnerability of the GBN to the different hazards. This vulnerability crossed with the exposure, finally allows to evaluate concretely the criticality of the GBN for each hazard through its components and then to propose solutions of adequate recommendations
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation

<i>Relevance</i>	<p>The LL has the KPI of: Support of biodiversity (Further described in D7.1 section 7.1.3). The KPI is advanced through the multiple green spaces located throughout the campus, including a green rooftop, a football field, and a community garden. In all the green areas, the use of native plants with low water requirements and with respect for the habitat typology are considered and encouraged.</p> <p>In particular, concerning the community garden, traditional growing methods will be used together with teaching how to farm without pesticides and herbicides. This approach will also be used in all gardening done at the 300.000 sqm of SONAE Campus.</p> <p>Concerning the Living Wall and underused brick walls at the campus, it is foreseen that these could be exploited as a lighthouse for biodiversity and promoting learning about species and other biodiversity-related issues.</p> <p>Finally, many birdhouses are expected to be installed throughout the campus</p>
<i>Impact</i>	<p>The application of the topic to the LL can be a way to support the KPI and focus points listed in the column to the left.</p> <p>In addition, the community garden is expected to serve as a hub for solidarity, team building, learning, and empowerment of the communities (the moon shooting stage might be out-of-scope).</p>
<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity life framework to assess and support the implementation of actions in favour of biodiversity and particularly on the topic of biophilia

Table 9. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Porto LL

4.4 LL 4 – Aarhus

Aarhus LL is located in a section of Aarhus University called the University City (in Danish: Universitetsbyen). The University city contains buildings, which previously have been housing a hospital. Through refurbishment, the buildings are being converted to support an extended range of activities related to the academic life at Aarhus University. Buildings 23, 24, 1850, 1830, 1810, and 1790 have been chosen as focal points for the LL.

The buildings are also called “the Kitchen 2.0” and “BSS” and have been chosen as the focal point because of their complementary to the PROBONO project in terms of the building phase, construction period, scale, and functionality. Table 10 presents the LL’s building characteristics.

Building	Role as AU LL	Building Phase	Construction Period	Building function
The Kitchen 2.0 Buildings 23,24	Confirmatory checks based on sensor data	In-use, while in early sketches phase for subsequent deep refurbishment	2022-2024	Start-up hub (café, mixed-use spaces for work, meetings, networking, events)
AU BSS Buildings 1850, 1830, 1810, 1790	Refurbishment, renovation tasks	Tender phase, deep renovation designs	2021 - 2025	Academic activities (lectures, offices, student workspaces)

Table 10. Characteristics of the Kitchen 2.0 and AU BSS

In the following, Table 11 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Aarhus LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	The topic is relevant to the LL since Human-centred ventilation simulation will be applied at both Kitchen 2.0 and BSS
<i>Impact</i>	The effect of including the topic in the LL is that the topic provides the possibility to evaluate if the buildings are fulfilling the users' requirements, as intended by the building design. The inclusion of the human-focused simulation and analysis provides the possibility to assess the occupant experience, which leads to addressing the trade-offs between occupant experience, environmental impact, and financial cost based on design decisions.
<i>Assessment</i>	As of today, the assessment of indoor comfort in Danish buildings is based on simulations of how many hours a year the room temperature exceeds previously defined operative temperatures as outlined in Vorre et al. [54].
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	The GBN maturity assessment, as described in D7.1, contains thematic parallels to the Danish DGNB certification. A focal point in the LL is to communicate the target green and socially beneficial impacts of the LL stakeholders (including design teams, occupants, students, staff, and AU management).
<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders.
<i>Assessment</i>	Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable. The current tool to assess the degree of sustainability of a neighbourhood and building used in the LL is the Danish DGNB system. The DGNB system provides the ability to assess concepts similar to the ones outlined in section 3.2. The use of DGNB provides the ability to assess how the building is performing within each of the six quality categories (environmental, economic, socio-cultural and functional, technical, process, and site), as well as how the building is performing in a total score based on the weighted average of the score in the six quality categories.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	The topic of climate adaption and resilience can be applied to the LL in relation to the DGNB certification of the buildings, since DGNB reward points in the Site criteria for assessing the risk and planning for future climate change.
<i>Impact</i>	The benefit of applying the tool to the LL would be that the climate adaptation resilience would be evaluated to ensure that the buildings are resilient to climate change since it is not mandatory to make this assessment in DGNB.
<i>Assessment</i>	A study of the climatic exposure of the LL based on the 8.5 scenario at the 2050 and 2070 horizons must be done to measure the climatic hazards for which the LL is the most vulnerable. Then, an analysis of the components of the GBN must be done, taking into account the sensitivity of the components to a hazard and its strategic importance on the good functionality of the GBN. This analysis of the components allows to obtain the vulnerability of the GBN to the different

	hazards. This vulnerability crossed with the exposure, finally allows to evaluate concretely the criticality of the GBN for each hazard through its components and then to propose solutions of adequate recommendations
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation
<i>Relevance</i>	PROBONO ambitions will accelerate TRL6 energy, material, and process innovations currently in focus for development in the Solar Panel Park, specifically: advanced methods of reducing loss in phase changing, combining solar harvesting and agriculture production, new ways of deploying solar panel infrastructure supporting biodiversity, acting as a visible "do-er" role model for Danish institutions.
<i>Impact</i>	The improvement of biodiversity at LL level is expected to provide, amongst other better conditions GBN users i.e. residents, personnel, visitors etc., health and well-being.
<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity construction framework to assess and support the implementation of actions in favour of biodiversity and particularly on the topic of biophilia

Table 11. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Aarhus LL

4.5 LL 5 – Brussels

The Brussel LL is focussed on the renovation of 2000 m² of the school building De l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole. Table 12 presents information on the characteristics of the buildings within the LL. The renovation focuses on making the renovated area useful for the school's educational needs while also being in line with the environmental and regulative requirements of the European Green Deal.

Building name	Building use	Year of construction	Net floor area (m2)	Occupant capacity
De l'Autre Côté de l'Ecole	Education	1990	7 300	600

Table 12. Characteristics of the buildings in Brussels LL

In the following, Table 13 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Brussels LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	The LL has the vision of showing the positive impact of data-driven knowledge on sustainability decision-making and how to maximise business and social innovation by influencing behaviour. The KPIs for the LL are being developed with WP6, but based on the description of the focus points of the KIP in D7.1, themes such as energy flexibility, and indoor environmental quality will be included in the KIP.
<i>Impact</i>	The use of human-focused simulation and analysis can provide the LL with the opportunity to address energy flexibility and indoor environmental impact through a holistic approach.

	Human-focused simulation and analysis can be used to ensure the best possible indoor climate in the eyes of the building users by providing the ability to simulate and document qualities in the indoor environment in a more flexible and nuanced way compared to existing approaches. The exact focus points of the human-focused simulation should be dependent on the LL's KIPs, but they could be related to: Thermal comfort, Visual comfort, Air quality, Acoustics.
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	The LL has the goal of meeting the highest standards of green innovation and the 2040 vision of the Brussels Government.
<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders. The LL can use the GBN maturity assessment to communicate, visualise, and assess to which degree the LL fulfils the objectives of being a GBN.
<i>Assessment</i>	Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	The KPIs for the LL har being developed with WP6, but based on the description of the focus points of the KIP in D7.1, climate resilience will be one of the themes which will be addressed in the KPIs.
<i>Impact</i>	n/a
<i>Assessment</i>	A study of the climatic exposure of the LL based on the 8.5 scenario at the 2050 and 2070 horizons must be done to measure the climatic hazards for which the LL is the most vulnerable. Then, an analysis of the components of the GBN must be done, taking into account the sensitivity of the components to a hazard and its strategic importance on the good functionality of the GBN. This analysis of the components allows to obtain the vulnerability of the GBN to the different hazards. This vulnerability crossed with the exposure, finally allows to evaluate concretely the criticality of the GBN for each hazard through its components and then to propose solutions of adequate recommendations
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation
<i>Relevance</i>	The KPIs for the LL are being developed with WP6, but based on the description of the focus points of the KPI in D7.1, biodiversity will be one of the themes that will be addressed in the KPIs. ACE has limited green spaces on the school premises. The green space consists of a courtyard-like backyard with an incline of 50 x 50 meters, by greening a roof during previous construction works. The artificially created green space contains planted greenery maintained by the students. Students utilize the space during breaks for relaxation and leisure, and it can be turned into an amphitheatre for outdoor school events. In addition, the high evaporative green roof is being discussed to be implemented on the roof of the LL during the PROBONO project.
<i>Impact</i>	Improving biodiversity at LL level is expected to provide, amongst other better conditions GBN users i.e. residents, personnel, visitors etc., health and well-being.

<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity construction framework to assess and support the implementation of actions in favour of biodiversity and particularly on the topic of biophilia.
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Table 13. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Brussels LL

4.6 LL 6 – Prague

The Prague living lab is focused on a building at the Czech Technical University in Prague, located in Dejvice, a North-Western urban area of Prague. The building houses the Faculty of Civil Engineering. Table 14 present information on the characteristics of the buildings within the LL. The LL will mainly focus on planning and Digital Twin development.

Building name	Building use	Year of construction	Net floor area (m ²)	Heated floor area (m ²)	Fenestration area (m ²)	Occupant capacity	Renovation construction method	Possibility for BIPV integration (Y/N)
Building B	Education	1970s	25 752	26 810	2910	3500 students	Pre-fabrication and standard renovation methods	Y

Table 14. Characteristics of the buildings in Prague LL

In the following, Table 15 presents the relevance, impact, and assessment of the four subtasks topics associated with PROBONO task T1.1 tailored for Prague LL.

Topic	Human-focused simulation and analysis
<i>Relevance</i>	The LL explores the solutions from Aarhus LL, but will maintain a focus on the Digital Twin development. The development of the Digital Twin includes optimizing the digital model to reach the optimal internal microclimate in the Building while minimizing energy consumption.
<i>Impact</i>	The effect of including human-focused simulation and analysis is that the topic provides the possibility to evaluate if the buildings are fulfilling the users' requirements based on the building design. Human-focused simulation and analysis allow for assessing the occupant experience within the selected focus points of the simulation and analysis. This can provide the ability to address the trade-offs between occupant experience, environmental impact, and financial cost based on design decisions. The focus points of the simulation and analysis should be based on the LL's specific KIPs, and can include themes such as thermal comfort, air quality, and visual comfort.
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	GBN maturity assessment
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.

<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic using the prepose matrix concept (as proposed in §3.2), can serve as a guide and visualization of the level/degree of maturity that the LL has reached in such a way that it is easily understandable by the stakeholders.
<i>Assessment</i>	Application of an assessment based on the proposed approach in §3.2 can be made for the next iteration of this deliverable.
Topic	Climate adaptation and resilience
<i>Relevance</i>	Information shared by the LL does not touch upon this subject.
<i>Impact</i>	n/a
<i>Assessment</i>	n/a
Topic	Biodiversity adaptation
<i>Relevance</i>	The LL's KPI has not been developed yet (as described in D7.1), but a point mentioned concerning the KPIs and the LL's impact is the intent to promote biodiversity through the building's green roof.
<i>Impact</i>	The application of the topic to the LL can be a way to support the intent to promote biodiversity on the green roof.
<i>Assessment</i>	Used of Biodiversity life framework to assess and support the implementation of actions in favour of biodiversity and particularly on the topic of biophilia

Table 15. The relevance, impact, and assessment survey of Prague LL

5 Specific use case studies from PROBONO LLs

This chapter presents the *application* or *assessment* of the subtasks defined in PROBONO task T1.1, which are tailored for specific use cases from PROBONO LLs.

5.1 Human-focused simulation and analysis

This section presents the case study of applying our ProFormalize framework (as presented in section 3.1.2) on cases from Aarhus LL and Dublin LL. The first three steps of the framework, elicitation, organisation and formalisation, are applied, and the cases from Aarhus LL are validated through a follow-up conversation with the interviewed architect.

5.1.1 Aarhus Living Lab

The following subsections present the steps in the use case from Aarhus LL. The use case has also been presented in our scientific research work in [53]

5.1.1.1 Elicitation

The elicitation stage was performed following the method outlined in Section 3.1.2. The elicitation resulted in the identification of 80 design arguments, spanning 7 locations. The locations are shown in Figure 16, and the number of collected arguments are summarised in Table 16.

Figure 16. A map of the visited locations during the interview, showing the sequence of the visited locations.

Location	No. of collected arguments
AU-HR	38
AU-MolBio	14
AU-CED	13
Nobel Park deli	8
Walkway under Randersvej	3
Nobel Park – Ringgaden – outdoor area	2
Nobel Park – External area	2
Total	80

Table 16. The visited locations and their corresponding number of collected design arguments.

5.1.1.2 Organization

Based on the elicitation, the organisation stage was performed following the method in Section 3.1.2, where parts of the interview describing social intents and design activities were added to the database of social intention. An excerpt of the database, showing 8 selected socially-oriented design arguments, are presented in Table 17, and Table 18 shows the 8 design arguments after the performance of the organization.

Building	DI	The socially-oriented design argument
AU-HR	1	There is a large sofa installed in front of the glass wall of the office. The sofa provides shelter and sitting spot, the department head office has privacy but is still open and accessible and not hidden.
	2	The window between the meeting room and the leader's room is placed so high up in the wall between them. Daylight gets through the window without the people in the meeting room being able to look into the office next door, keeping privacy in the leader's office.
	3	There are some seats in the third floor's entrance area. The building users will sit and be social in the intended area.
AU-MolBio	4	The hallway is divided visually by the installation of artwork on the wall. Walking though the hallway should be an experience.
	5	There is a coloured line of paint wrapping around the corner. The building users will feel curious about what is it around the corner.
	6	There is a sofa that contains electrical outlets. The students should enjoy using the space.
AU-CED	7	There are sofas and tables that can be used as a workplace for small meetings, online meetings and lunch. Making the building users want to come and work from office instead of working from home.
	8	There are acoustic panels in the area to make good acoustic environment. Make the building users want to come and work from the office instead of working from home.

Table 17. Organization of 8 selected design arguments, showing the social values and the corresponding design activities.

Building	DI	Design activity	Social value/intention
AU-HR	1	There is a large sofa installed in front of the glass wall of the office, providing shelter and a sitting spot	The department head office has privacy but is still open and accessible and not hidden.
	2	The window between the meeting room and the leader's room is high up	Keeping privacy in the leader's office.

		in the wall. Daylight gets through it without affecting visual privacy.	
	3	There are some seats in the third floor's entrance area.	The building users will sit and be social in the intended area.
AU-MolBio	4	The hallway is divided visually by the installation of artwork on the wall.	Walking through the hallway should be an experience.
	5	There is a coloured line of paint wrapping around the corner.	The building users will feel curiosity about what is it around the corner.
	6	There is a sofa that contains electrical outlets.	The students should enjoy using the space.
AU-CED	7	There are sofas and tables that can be used as a workplace for small meetings, online meetings and lunch.	Make the building users want to come and work from office instead of working from home.
	8	There are acoustic panels in the area to make a good acoustic environment.	Make the building users want to come and work from office instead of working from home.

Table 18. Organization of 8 selected design arguments, showing the social values and the corresponding design activities.

5.1.1.3 Formalization of the arguments

The formalization of the first design argument (DI1) is presented below, the formalization of the remaining seven design arguments (DI2 to DI8) are presented in Appendix A

DI1 - *There is a large sofa installed in front of the glass wall of the office. The sofa provides shelter and sitting spot, the department head office has privacy but is still open and accessible and not hidden*, illustrated in Figure 17. This case is an example of a **preserving causal relationship**. The formalization of the argument is presented in Figure 18. The formalization was performed according to the following: There is the head office (HO), a glass wall (GW) and a sofa (S) that is in front of the glass wall of the office. There are also two slabs, a Slab (SI1) representing the entrance area and a slab (SI2) representing the area on which the sofa is placed. There is an occupant (P) representing an occupant sitting on the sofa, an occupant (Q) representing an occupant in the head's office and an occupant (Z) representing an occupant in the movement space of the entrance (Slab (SI1)). The functional space of the sofa (S) from the perspective of the occupant (P) creates the sitting spot. The visible space of the working space of the head's office and the movement space of the entrance area (slab (SI1)) should be **disjoint**, hence keeping privacy. The office is still visible for an occupant who is using the sitting spot, so the office is still accessible and not hidden.

Figure 17. A floor plan of the second floor of the AU-HR building showing the sofa and the window between the leader's room and the meeting room.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
office (HO)	occupant (P)	comfort (funcF1)
sofa (S)	occupant (Q)	privacy (funcF2)
glassWall (GW)	occupant (Z)	Awareness (funcM)
inFront (S, GW)	funcF1 = functionalSpace (S, P)	
slab (S11)	funcV1 = visibleSpace (HO, P)	
slab (S12)	funcF2 = workSpace (HO, Q)	
on (S, S12)	funcV2 = visibleSpace (funcF2, Z)	
disjoint (funcM, funcV2)	funcM = movementSpace (S11, Z)	

Figure 18. Formalization of D11.

5.1.1.4 Evaluation

As the last stage of the case study, an evaluation interview with the interviewed architect was conducted with the aim of this interview was to validate and improve the set of formalized socially-oriented design arguments. During the interview, the 8 design intentions, were

presented to the interviewee and the interviewee was asked to comment on the three parameters; clarity, accuracy and the level of capturing the social intention behind each design argument. The insights from the evaluation is as follows:

- Explaining the concept of having "several layers of goals" in most of the arguments. The architect emphasized on this concept especially in the cases where several building elements were used, each contributes in achieving the goal. This agrees with our definition of chain and common-effect causal relationships.
- The architect explained the idea of using a quality that is available in a certain space and extend it to neighboring spaces, without affecting the level of quality in the original space. This agrees with our logic of "preserving causal relationships".
- The architect elaborated on the "chain causal relationship" as he argued that in some cases, the goal is to make the building occupants aware of the availability of a certain social value and therefore they can expand its applicability somewhere else.
- The architect added more levels of details when asked about some design activities, such additions will be applied accordingly in the current overall list of design arguments.
- The architect was asked about his views on what a potential software platform that implements this framework would help architects with. His idea was that a computer tool would help architects recognize the importance of satisfying basic design needs before starting to invest in additional higher level qualities. That is, if the basic needs of a certain space (or the base line needs as he said) are not met, the extra (affiliating) added qualities that were intended to enhance the experience of that space will not work.
- The architect elaborated on the idea of having a clearer connection between the product-level elements that create a visible space and the different visual abilities of occupants. For example, considering the case that occupants have different levels of eye sight, height, etc.
- When asked about a specific domain-level predicate and what he can make of it, his answer was that the current level of detail is basic and understandable but lacking the connection with a specific context.
- The architect was also asked if the goal level predicate used in each argument captures the value or the effect intended. In most cases the architect agreed with what we used and in some cases he suggested including additional goals that might be more implicit.

5.1.2 Dublin Living Lab

5.1.2.1 Elicitation

The elicitation stage was performed following the method outlined in Section 3.2.1. The elicitation resulted in the identification of 1 design argument in the Harbour Lodge building, in the Dublin LL. The locations are shown on the map in Figure 16.

Figure 19. Map marking the location of the Harbour Lodge building in Dún Laoghaire, Dublin.

5.1.2.2 Organization

Based on the elicitation, the organisation stage was performed following the method in Section 3.1.2, where parts of the interview describing social intents and design activities were added to the database of social intentions, the organization of the intent are presented in Table 19 and Table 20.

Building	DI	The socially-oriented design argument
Harbour Lodge	HL	Respect the existing design of the building (the building is protected) while making it more comfortable for the people working in the building, with a focus on thermal comfort.

Table 19. Overview of the socially-oriented design argument for the design intention in the Harbour Lodge building.

Building	DI	Design activity	Social value/intention
Harbour Lodge	HL	Install double glazed windows in the existing window frames. Adding insulation in the external walls.	Make building users be in thermal comfort when working from the office, while at the same time keeping the building heritage visible.

Table 20. Organization of the design argument from the Harbour Lodge, showing the social value and the corresponding design activities.

5.1.2.3 Formalization of the arguments

The formalization of the design argument from the Harbour lodge are presented below.

DI-HL - *Respect the existing design of the building (the building is protected) while making it more comfortable for the people working in the building, with a focus on thermal.* This case is at the same time and example of a **preserving causal relationship** and a **common-effect causal relationship**. The formalization was performed according to the following: There are glazed windows (GWin) that are installed on external walls (W), these walls are also insulated using insulation (I). The heat loss is also calculated, and this is represented using a predicate called "heatLossCal", which takes the building element that is required to have its heat loss calculated (i.e., glazed windows (GWin) in this case). There is also a clear requirement concerning all building elements (e.g., external walls, internal walls, etc.), which is to keep changes minimal in order to preserve the history and the heritage of the building. This is represented using the "requirement" predicate.

Both the glazed windows and the wall insulation will generate spaces where the temperature is reasonable. These spaces are represented using the "tempSpace" predicate. The building occupant should have a feeling of comfort (represented using the "comfort" predicate) as long as they are inside the area that represents the union of the individual generated spaces (i.e., the union of the tempSpace generated by the glazed windows and the tempSpace generated by the wall insulation). Figure 20 presents the floorplan of the ground floor of the building, along with pictures of the changing of the window glazing and where additional isolation has been added.

Figure 20. Floor plan of the ground floor of the Harbour Lodge and pictures of the activities described in Table 20.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
externalWall (W) glazedWindow (GWin) insulation (I) add (I, W) add (GWin, W) heatLossCal (GWin) requirement (heritage)	occupant (P) FuncT1 = tempSpace (Gwin) FuncT2 = tempSpace (I) FuncU = union (FuncT1, funcT2) FuncI = inside (P, FuncU)	comfort (FuncI)

Figure 21. Formalization of DI HL.

5.2 GBN maturity assessment

We share below the assessments done at the time of producing the deliverable. It is deemed interesting to do another assessment yearly during the course of the project (and possibly later on) to assess the progress on the GBN journey of the living labs. To date, some Living Labs have received and reviewed their assessments (Aarhus), some have not reviewed them so far (Madrid, Prague, Porto), and others are yet to start (Brussels, Dublin).

5.2.1 Aarhus Living Lab

5.2.1.1 Vision and activities

The mapping of the Living Lab vision (D7.2) and activities (based on D5.1 Digital Twin Use cases) was done, first using the PROBONO automated assessment tool, then reviewed by the Living Lab stakeholders. This was captured as the mapping in Figure 22.

Figure 22. Comparing AAR UC (circles) to vision (stars). Size indicates the relative importance on a Likert scale.

5.2.1.2 Organisation review

The questionnaire described in section 3.2 has been also applied to a number of the Living Lab stakeholders. As a reminder, there were 32 questions, split into four big themes described in Figure 23.

Figure 23. SWOT of the organization.

One can see that the LL ranks itself on an average of level 2 on a range from 1 to 5 (likert scale). The “GBN Purpose” ranks a level higher on average.

Exploring a level deeper, one can observe variability in observations, as seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Detailed SWOT of the organization.

The survey does indicate an average score in the different components for each of the four themes, again indicating variability in the answers, but also signalling strong identify points of the Living Lab, for example on Point 3.1 (Leadership and governance) or Point 1.1 (Delivering

integrated services) while some points are areas of interest (such as Point 2.4 Privacy and security or Point 3.2 IT and Data) are highlighted.

This survey will unlock additional value when administered to more individuals, as well as benchmarking it compared to other LLs.

5.2.1.3 Feedback from the Living Lab

*"We believe the Maturity assessment was certainly helpful! The reason is very simple: It helped us to assess **where we stand now and where we are heading to** when the aim is working with as well as maturing on a GBN concept and in **which way our activities are contributing to advance it further.***

*In fact, after using the tool, one very interesting discovery for us was about **the need to review and find a better alignment** between our current individual activities (in the framework of the PROBONO project) and what we had earlier defined and elaborated on the scope or vision of our AU LL.*

This also gave us a heads up related to the impact of our activities (in PROBONO) and a lot of other activities that are under development within the LLs but not necessarily in the framework of the PROBONO project."

5.2.2 **Porto Living Lab**

5.2.2.1 Vision and activities

Figure 25. Comparing Porto Activities to Vision (stars) to Activities (circles) form all deliverables. Size indicates the relative importance on a Likert scale.

The preliminary mapping in Figure 25 are based on D7.12, which is the result of the automated process led by our tool. It does not yet include human review but interestingly hints at a strong alignment between the Vision (stars) and Activities (circles). There is a star but not a corresponding circle in the top left corner (Attractiveness and Governance); this means that topics around might want to be reviewed and possibly reprioritized or realigned, as covered in the next section.

5.2.2.2 Use of other deliverables inputs as a tool to support activities identification

Figure 26 captures the different topics captured in the Social and Behavioral Innovations.

Figure 26. Mapping D2.3 activities (circles). The size is relative to the importance on a Likert scale.

This visual support can help, for example, the Porto Living Lab to identify innovations to address the first point (Attractiveness / Governance, top left of the matrix, circled) and find a solution for their identified need.

5.2.3 Preliminary mapping of other Living Labs

Similar, early reviews of Prague (Figure 27) and Madrid (Figure 28) Living Labs’ programme of activities and vision were conducted, as captured below. Side by side comparison allow to identify similarities and differences between the visions of each Living Lab.

Figure 27. Draft mapping of Prague LL. Comparison of the Prague Activities to Visions (stars) to Activities (circles) from all deliverables. The size is relative to the importance of a Likert scale (refer to section 3.2.3.1 for details on how to read and interpret these assessment tables).

Figure 28. Draft mapping of Madrid LL. Comparison of Madris UC (circles) to vision (stars). The size is relative to the importance on a Likert scale (refer to section 3.2.3.1 for details on how to read and interpret these assessment tables).

5.3 Climate adaptation and resilience

When considering climate change risks, several dimensions are combined. Based on the Centre for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning (CEREMA) approach, we consider Criticality as the interaction between the physical vulnerability of a system, exposure to the hazard over time, and the nature of the hazard itself, along with the probability of its manifestation. Therefore, we consider Criticality as follows:

$$\text{Criticality} = \text{Hazard} \& \text{Exposure} \cdot \text{Physical Vulnerability}$$

Hazard and Exposure are the first aspects one works through to develop a climate change risk analysis. The dimension of hazard and exposure entails the likelihood of physical exposure linked to hazards. In the absence of physical exposure, regardless of the severity of the hazard event, there is no risk. Hence, merging the hazard and exposure aspects into a unified dimension is coherent.

It is required to categorize exposure indicators into two families: simple and composite. Simple exposure indicators are based on open data sources that provide spatial data, which are thereafter spatially downscaled to improve the resolution of the spatial data. Composite indicators are combinations of several simple indicators (also called composites) that are combined to form more complex indicators.

Exposure indicators are classified under five classes and are designed according to literature reviews and experts' previous experiences. When there is no scientific-based evidence to design the five classes, they are broken down under the Natural Breaks (Jenks) mode or the Quantile mode. Natural Breaks tries to find natural groupings of data to create classes. The resulting classes will be such that there will be maximum variance between individual classes and the least variance within each class. Quantile will decide the classes such that number of values in each class are the same. If there are 1000 values and we want 4 classes, quantile method will decide the classes such that each class will have 250 values. Thereafter, you apply the average classification of each exposure layer of the same indicator you have to obtain a standardized classification. For instance, if you have a maximum temperature exposure indicator with four layers (SSP2-4.5 horizon 2030 and 2050 and SSP5-8.5 horizon 2030 and 2050), it is required to do the average of the four classes). Finally, it is necessary to normalise the class with a 0-5 range to have a similar classification for each indicator.

The list of indicators and their corresponding methodologies are as follows:

Air quality indicators are simple indicators from the Copernicus Sentinel-5 Precursor mission European Space Agency (2023) [55]The inaugural mission of the Copernicus Sentinel-5 Precursor is dedicated to the continual observation of Earth's atmosphere. The primary aim of the Copernicus Sentinel-5P mission is to conduct detailed atmospheric measurements at high spatiotemporal resolutions. These measurements are intended for various applications, including air quality assessment, monitoring of ozone and UV radiation levels, and climate analysis and forecasting.

Heatwaves is a simple exposure indicator from the Climate Change Knowledge Portal of World Bank Group (2023)[56]The official name for this indicator is Warm Spell Duration Index (days), which corresponds to the number of days in a sequence of 6 or more days in which the daily maximum temperature exceeds the 90th percentile of the reference period. After processing the data, we engage in spatial downscaling to improve the spatial resolution of the layer.

Marine submersion is a composite indicator studied under scenarios SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 for the years 2050 and 2070, where sea level changes according to the NASA Sea Level Projection Tool (2023) [57] were extracted. To determine areas that will be affected, the digital elevation model of the study areas obtained from ASTER at 30 m resolution was considered as baseline material and the corresponding sea level rise heights were added to obtain submersion risks.

Below, Figure 29, is a submersion map in Dublin for the horizons 2050 and 2070 under the scenarios SSP2-4.5 and SSP-5-8.5.

Figure 29 : Submersion risk map of Dublin at the horizons 2050 and 2070 under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5

Strong winds is a simple exposure indicator from the Climate Data Store of the Copernicus (2021) [58]. The official name for this indicator is Near-surface wind speed ($m\ s^{-1}$) which corresponds to the magnitude of the two-dimensional horizontal air velocity near the surface. After processing the data, we engage in a spatial downscaling to improve the spatial resolution of the layer.

Below is a map of the indicator Near-surface wind speed in Madrid (Figure 30). We can appreciate a reduction of wind speed between 2050 and 2070. Climate change can have varied effects on wind speed depending on the specific region and atmospheric conditions. However, in general, climate change tends to increase wind speeds. However, it's important to note that the impact of climate change on wind speed can vary depending on factors such as geographic location, terrain, and local weather patterns. Some regions may experience decreases in wind speed or changes in wind direction due to complex interactions between atmospheric and oceanic circulation patterns influenced by climate change.

Figure 30 : Near-surface wind speed for the horizons 2050 and 2070 under the scenario SSP2-4.5

River flooding is a composite indicator where a historical analysis has been done on the area for floodwater occurrence at 30 meters spatial resolution. We produced a map of the location and temporal distribution of surface water from 1984 to 2023 and provided statistics on the extent and change of those water surfaces through time. This data was generated using 7,785 scenes from Landsat 4, 5, 7, and 8. Each pixel was individually classified into water / non-water using an expert system, and we produced 4 distinct images:

- Water occurrence: The frequency with which water was present. Range between 0 and 100%.
- Water max extent: Binary image containing 1 anywhere water has ever been detected. 0 for no water and 1 for water.
- Water seasonality: Number of months water is present. Range between 0 and 12.
- Water recurrence: The frequency with which water returns from year to year. Range between 0 and 100%.

Flood map indicators: Along with the land classification and the historical analysis already established, we developed an algorithm to derive the severity pixel by pixel of flooding in the study area. This algorithm uses elevation, slope, precipitation projection, distance from river, flow accumulation points, evapotranspiration, and land cover classification.

Elevation and slope were derived from NASA SRTM Digital Elevation 30m, precipitation and consecutive dry days projections for the 2030, 2050, 2070 years at RCP 4.5 and 8.5 were derived from CMIP6, distance from rivers was derived from WWF HydroSHEDS Free Flowing Rivers Network v1, flow accumulation was derived from WWF HydroSHEDS Flow Accumulation, 15 Arc-Seconds, evapotranspiration was derived from MOD16A2.006: Terra Net Evapotranspiration 8-Day Global 500m.

These inputs were compounded, and they were assigned severity indicators ranging between 1 and 5, where 1 is considered to have a very low chance of flooding, and 5 is considered to have a very high chance of flooding. These results were used in an equation where each indicator was given a weight out of 100, and a final severity number was calculated. This severity number indicates which areas will be flooded first in certain flooding scenarios.

Along with the flood severity indicator, we produced riverine and coastal flooding projections for 2050 and 2070 at RCP 4.5 and 8.5 with 10, 50, and 100 return periods.

Flood Risk formula: $(\text{Slope} \cdot 0.2) + (\text{Precipitation} \cdot 0.15) + (\text{Precipitation} > 20\text{mm} \cdot 0.05) + (\text{Precipitation} > 50\text{mm} \cdot 0.1) + (\text{LandCover} \cdot 0.05) + (\text{FlowDirection} \& \text{Accumulation} \cdot 0.15) + (\text{EvapoTranspiration} \cdot 0.15) + (\text{ConsecutiveDryDays} \cdot 0.15)$

- Slope: Degrees
- Precipitation: maximum precipitation per pixel in mm/year at different scenarios
- Precipitation > 20mm: maximum number of days where precipitation per pixel is higher than 20mm/day at different scenarios

- Precipitation>50mm: maximum number of days where precipitation per pixel is higher than 50mm/day at different scenarios
- Landcover: Level4 landcover map
- FlowDirection&Accumulation: Water accumulation points for each pixel
- EvapoTranspiration: Maximum evapotranspiration per pixel in mm/year at different scenarios
- ConsecutiveDryDays: Maximum number of consecutive dry days per year at different scenarios

Freeze-Thaw is a composite exposure indicator using composites from the Climate Change Knowledge Portal of World Bank Group [56]. The first composite used is the Number of Ice Days ($T_{max} < 0^{\circ}\text{C}$), which corresponds to the average count of days when the daily maximum temperature did not break through the freezing point but remained below 0°C . The second is Minimum Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), which corresponds to the average minimum temperature. Each composite is spatially downscaled prior to being used together. The formula is as follows: Number of ice days \cdot Tmin.

Vulnerability is used to evaluate the criticality of an asset to a climate hazard, the LL in this case. According to the UNDRR, vulnerability corresponds to the “*conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards.*” (UNDRR, 2021) [59].

In the climate change framework, the IPCC defined vulnerability as “*the degree to which a system is susceptible to, or unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extreme*” [60]. In this context, the vulnerability of an asset is a function of its sensitivity to be affected, either adversely or beneficially, by climate variability or change; and the adaptive capacity to adjust to climate change impacts, to moderate potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to cope with consequences.

5.3.1 Climate physical vulnerability assessment for Dublin and Aarhus Living Labs

Based on the definitions presented in the previous section, this section undertakes a rough climate physical vulnerability assessment for Dublin and Aarhus LL. To do that, a physical sensitivity assessment of each LL needs to be carried out. Therefore, each LL is divided into systems (e.g., building infrastructure) that contain critical subsystems and structural components. This step is necessary to gauge how sensitive each component of the LL is to different types of hazards.

It should be noted that the sensitivity of systems and their structural components is adjusted based on aggravating factors regarding a hazard that could affect the LL integrity and functionality e.g., structural conditions (age, materials, maintenance, etc.), geological and topographic features (terrain, soil type, slope, etc.), or maintenance practices. The evaluation of sensitivity and aggravating factors is generally more accurate when stakeholders and communities are involved in the process of evaluation.

The sensitivity of a component impacted by a hazard is evaluated on a scale of 0 to 4, where 0 implies no impact at all and 4 is completely damaged or destroyed. An elaboration of the scale is seen in Table 21.

Score	Class	Sensitivity
0	Very Low	Minimal to no impact on the component, which is highly resilient and adaptable to various climate conditions.
1	Low	Impact(s) may cause easily repairable damage and minor inconveniences to services associated with the affected asset. Require cleaning, minor reparation and control of the proper functioning
2	Moderate	Impact(s) may cause repairable damage and inconveniences to services associated with the affected assets, while not suffering immediate negative impacts.
3	High	Impact(s) are likely to cause significant damage to system elements, requiring substantial repair or replacement efforts of the component.
4	Very High	Impact(s) are expected to inflict extensive damage, potentially exceeding the repairable threshold for system component. Associated services will experience severe disruptions and significant losses, with potential long-term consequences. It will require the new construction or installation of the component.

Table 21. Overview of the scale for evaluating component sensitivity.

A component of the LL is vulnerable when it is exposed to a hazard and sensitive to damage. By considering both exposure and sensitivity, vulnerability assessment provides a holistic understanding of the potential risks associated with the LL in connection with climate hazards. In this sense, vulnerability can be directly obtained as a product of exposure metrics to hazards and the sensitivity of components to those hazards. In this regard, a system breakdown is proposed for Dublin and Aarhus LL based on their description provided in section 4.

- **Dublin**

Dublin LL is an interconnected network of municipal buildings, located in the south-eastern part of the city on the Irish sea coast. The sensitivity assessment for Dublin LL is based on a cluster of 5 buildings: County Hall, Ferry Terminal, Lexicon Library, Harbour Master’s Building and Social Housing.

Figure 31. Dublin LL- Country Hall

- **Aarhus:**

Aarhus LL corresponds to a section of the Aarhus University mainly composed by a set of two buildings: *The Kitchen 2.0* and *AU BSS*, corresponding to the biggest start-up of Aarhus and the School of Business and Social Sciences at Aarhus University, respectively.

Figure 32. Aarhus University, *The Kitchen* (up-left) and *AU BSS* (bottom-left)

From this information, Dublin and Aarhus LL were divided into 4 main systems:

- Building infrastructure
- Utilities
- Transportation
- Recreational and green spaces

Dublin LL also included an Information Technology (IT) system. Then, for each system, subsystems and components are defined and their sensitivity to different climate hazards evaluated. Details regarding the components and the values of sensitivity could be adjusted and attributed from infrastructure experts experience and interviews with local stakeholders.

A complete and detailed sensitivity evaluation for each climate hazard and LL including the impact and impact mechanism affecting the component is in Appendix B, and the evaluation for Dublin LL (Table 22) and Aarhus LL (Table 23) is presented below.

Dublin LL System			Air quality	Heatwaves	Marine submersion	Strong winds	River flooding	Clay swelling and shrinking	Freeze-Thaw	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature
System	Sub-systems	Component	Structural sensitivity							
Building infrastructure: County Hall, Ferry Terminal, Lexicon Library, Harbour Master's Building, Social Housing	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	3	1	2	3	4	2	2	2
	Interieur finishing materials	Flooring, walls, ceilings, etc	2	1	1	3	3	2	3	0
	Isolation system	Isolation material	2	1	1	1	3	2	2	4
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	4
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	2	4	4	1	4	2	1	1
	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	2	3	4	3	4	2	4	4
Utilities	Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	1	1	3	0	2	2	4	3

	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning	Air handlers, chillers, filters	3	3	2	1	4	1	4	4
	Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	4	3	0	2	2	1		4
Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking	2	1	3	2	3	4	2	1
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways	2	1	1	1	3	4	2	1
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities	3		1	3	1	4		3
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	1
	Ferry Terminal	Ferry Terminal (cross-channel ferries, arrival point, transportation links)	3	2		4	1	3	3	1
Recreational and green spaces	Parks and open spaces	Landscaping features	1	4	2	4	3	1	4	4
		Recreational amenities	1	2	2	4	3	2	2	3

Table 22. Sensitivity evaluation for each climate hazard for Dublin LL.

Aarhus LL System			Air quality	Heatwaves	Marine submersion	Strong winds	River flooding	Clay swelling and shrinking	Freeze-Thaw	Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature
System	Sub-systems	Component	Structural sensitivity							
Building infrastructure: Administrative buildings e.g., offices, academic buildings e.g., class rooms or lectures halls, libraries, etc research facilities e.g., laboratories, student accomodation	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	1	4	3	3	3	3	4	3
	Interieur finishing materials	Flooring, walls, ceilings, etc	0	3	3	3	2	2	2	2
	Isolation system	Isolation material	1	2		2	3	2	3	3
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	3	1		3	3	2		
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	3	1	4	1	4	2	1	
Utilities	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	3	3	4	2	4	0	4	4
	Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	1	0	3	1	1	1	4	3
	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning	Air handlers, chillers, filters	4	4	3	1	2	2	3	3

	Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	3				1		
Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking		3	3	3		2	2
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways	0	3	4	1		3	2
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities			4	1		2	2
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms	2	2	2	3		2	2
Information Technology (IT) Infrastructure	Servers systems	Servers and data storage	1	3	2	2		0	2
	Networking equipment	Networking switches and routers	1	3	2	2		0	2
	Computers and peripherals	Computers (desktops, laptops)	0	2	2	2			2
Recreational and green spaces	Parks and open spaces	University Park, botanical and community gardens	3	4		2			2
		Sports Fields	1	3	0	2	0		3

Table 23. Sensitivity evaluation for each climate hazard for Aarhus LL.

6 Conclusion

This document primarily presented a list of key aspects and elements of GBNs, such as vision, stakeholders, transition, sustainability, biodiversity, etc., related to the overall scope and objective of the PROBONO project. Concept, practical, and target GBNs were described. The major conclusion of this deliverable that we highlight is that: the applied methods of social-value capture (i.e., ProFormalise), the assessment of maturity and climate and biodiversity adaptations, capturing the essence of living places services and sustainability, is a strong base to capture what human-centric, sustainable Green Building Neighbourhoods can be.

Four green certification systems were reviewed and compared, showing how the systems make trade-offs in balancing three major pillars of environmental, economic, and societal sustainability: BREEAM, LEED, DGNB, and Nordic Swan. An initial stakeholder map was presented, including roles such as Private Finance, Local Authority, Local Business and citizens, and Architect, and was extended with the Mediator and GBN Integrator roles. This map will be used in the next phase to identify key stakeholders, in particular GBNs.

In this regard, it is expected that the report will be distributed to all project partners to help them broaden their understanding of GBNs and the PROBONO project (as a particularly large project with all 47 partners and six LLs). This is also an attempt to find out the overlaps between the working groups, tasks, partners, and primary and secondary objectives of the LLs to facilitate and improve collaboration between specific project partners.

An introduction to the context and background of the subtasks of task T1.1 was presented. It was reported that simulation and analysis tools are most often applied to: architectural design, HVAC design, Building Performance ratings (e.g. green certification), building stock analysis and CFD. A broad framework was presented for how performance-based simulation tools can be applied. These typical use categories, application framework, and a set of ten key questions are intended to provide an entry point for particular GBNs to identify an appropriate set of simulation and analysis tools tailored to their cases. A review of the human-centred design framework based on social sustainability factors was presented, towards addressing more concrete concepts related to social sustainability and values, divided into actions and impacts working on three different levels. With this perspective, a preliminary comparison between the certification systems of DGNB Denmark, BREEAM, LEED, and the WELL building standard showed that the social qualities which are addressed in each of these certification systems have large

overlaps when compared on the level of the qualities, with the largest difference between the certification systems assessment of social qualities being based on the different traditions, and regulations that the certification systems are based on. Finally, a human-centred design framework was introduced, which can be used to capture and formalize the socially oriented design intentions through the design stages to ensure that the socially oriented intentions do not get lost when stakeholders change.

The GBN Maturity Matrix was presented, which will be used to assess particular GBNs and provide benchmarks for subsequent discussions and decision-making. It is developed by building on the Smart Infrastructure Index, and explicitly addresses aspects such as People coordination, Process, Technology, Culture, etc., across five levels.

Climate adaption and resilience in the context of GBNs was presented by developing an initial set of metrics for risk, sensitivity and vulnerability based on internationally accepted standards. Selected indicators deemed to be central to GBNs are air quality, heatwaves, marine submersion, strong winds, river flooding, clay swelling and shrinking, freeze-thaw, and monthly mean minimum temperature. The future evolution of the selected indicators will be modelled using IPCC scenarios (specifically SSP 2-4.5 and SSP 5-8.5). A review of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon and how this can be understood in terms of GBNs was presented, including mitigation and adaptation strategies based on (for example) passive cooling techniques. The overall framework of indicators and strategies will subsequently be used by particular GBNs for enhanced resilience.

The urgent need for biodiversity in the context of GBNs was presented, emphasising the impact of climate change on human health and well-being in urban areas, and so on. BiodiverCity (R) certification tools and guidelines were presented with the intended impact being based on three approaches: to broaden reflection on environmental topics; to build and run buildings and eco-neighbourhoods in a way that promotes biodiversity; to add value while emphasizing the services rendered.

Section 4 presented the relevance, impact, and assessment of the above key areas (aligned with the subtasks ST1.1.1-ST1.1.4) tailored for PROBONO LLs and extended them by applying and assessing them on some specific use cases from PROBONO LLs (section 5). The evaluation of the human-centred design framework, ProFormalize, by actual key stakeholders, helped to ensure a fair assessment. The assessment was positive, along with constructive feedback on aspects that are being improved with ProFormalize. The proposed approaches for the assessment of maturity and climate and biodiversity adaptations capture both the perception of the GBN

leaders to deliver on their promise and a robust, internationally demonstrated base to demonstrate the commitment of resources to the actions aligned with the GBN vision, which can promote climate resiliency and biodiversity, encourage the development of natural spaces, and create liveable cities. These approaches are particularly scale-free, which allows us to demonstrate the continuum of, for example, specific technologies or initiatives, possibly at a building level, to the overarching European objectives and how each action in the GBN contributes to sustainable neighbourhoods' services.

Our research work on a critical comparison of concepts and approaches to social sustainability in the construction industry forms the basis for the development of a novel method, SEEDS (Socio-Environmental Early-stage Decision Support). SEEDS is intended to act as a tool for decision support and inspiration in the early design stages by consisting of a catalogue which presents an overview of social intentions, their corresponding design activities and associated environmental impacts, and an overview to what degree the social intentions are realised in existing projects. SEEDS will, therefore, support early design stakeholders in making informed and evidence-based decisions regarding risks and consequences associated with the inclusion of socially oriented design intentions in the design of future sustainable buildings and neighbourhoods.

The next step related to the human-centred design framework, ProFormalize, will be to develop it through a software plugin that will be integrated into a prominent BIM-based software design tool in the AECO industry (e.g., Revit). This plugin will serve two purposes: the first one is to enable architects to digitally capture and include their socially oriented design intentions into the digital representation of buildings, and the second is to visualize these intentions within the 3D visualisation of the BIM model, and thereby to make them accessible to other stakeholders in the design team, and modifiable in the design phase of building construction. ProFormalise plugin tool will facilitate communication of design intentions that are often implicit in conventional design procedures and are prone to be lost.

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Appendix A

Formalisation of DI2 to DI8, referenced in section 5.1.1.

DI2 - *The window between the meeting room and the leader’s room is placed so high up in the wall between them. Daylight gets through the window without the people in the meeting room being able to look into the office next door, keeping privacy in the leader’s office*, illustrated in *Figure 17*. This case is an example of a **preserving causal relationship**. The formalization of the of the argument are presented in *Figure 33*.The formalization were performed according to the following: There is a meeting room (MR), a leader's room (LR) and they are adjacent. There is a window (Win1) which is in the wall (W1) in the leader's room, from which daylight gets in. There is a second window (Win2) located high up in the wall (W2) between the meeting room (MR) and the leader's room (LR). Both rooms have their own work space (in which their corresponding occupant can work). Occupant (P) is an occupant of the meeting room (MR) and occupant (Q) is an occupant of the leader's room (LR). The visibility space of the working space of the leader's room (LR) and the working space of the meeting room (MR) should be **disjoint**, that is, an occupant (P) who is in the work space of the meeting room should not be able to see the work space of the adjacent leader's room (LR) and the other way around. Hence keeping privacy. There is a light space coming from the first window (Win1) in the leader's room (LR) representing the daylight. This light space intersects the window (Win2) in the wall between the rooms and hence creating another light space inside the meeting room (MR). The intersection between the light space coming from (Win2) and the work space of the meeting room (MR) gives the daylight access intended value.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
meetingRoom (MR)	occupant (P)	daylightAccess (funcI2)
leaderRoom (LR)	occupant (Q)	privacy (funcF1)
adjacent (MR, LR)	funcF1 = workSpace (MR, P)	privacy (funcF2)
window (Win1)	funcF2 = workSpace (LR, Q)	
window (Win2)	funcL = lightSpace (Win1)	
wall (W1)	funcI = intersection (funcL, Win2)	
wall (W2)	funcL2 = lightSpace (Win2)	
in (Win1, W1)	funcI2 = intersection (funcF1, funcL2)	
in (Win2, W2)	funcV1 = visibilitySpace (funcF1, P)	
position (Win2, high)	funcV2 = visibilitySpace (funcF2, Q)	
disjoint (funcF1, funcV2)		
disjoint (funcF2, funcV1)		

Figure 33. Formalization of DI2.

DI3 - *There are some seats in the third floor’s entrance area. The building users will sit and be social in the intended area*, illustrated in *Figure 34*. This case is an example of a **chain causal relationship**. The formalization of the of the argument are presented in *Figure 35*.The

formalization were performed according to the following: This argument was formalized according to the following: There are chairs (Ch) in the entrance (slab(SI)) of the room. Occupant (P) will see that they can sit there and use that space. This as a result creates an opportunity for social interaction as well.

Figure 34. A floor plan of the third floor of the AU-HR building showing the seating area.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
chair (Ch)	occupant (P)	usage (funcI)
slab (Sl)	funcF = functionalSpace (Ch)	socialInteraction (funcI)
on (Ch, S)	funcV = visibleSpace (funcF)	
	funcI = inside (P, funcV)	

Figure 35. Formalization of DI3.

DI4 - The hallway is divided visually by the installation of artwork on the wall. Walking through the hallway should be an experience, illustrated in Figure 36. This case is an example of a **basic causal relationship**. The formalization of the argument is presented in Figure 37. The formalization were performed according to the following: There is a slab (SI) representing the hallway, a wall (W) installed on that slab and artwork (A) installed on the wall (W). There is an occupant (P) who is moving inside the movement space of the slab and at the same time they are inside the visible space of the artwork. This intersection between the movement space of the hallway slab (SI) and the visible space of the artwork (A) creates the desired experience for the occupant (P), which is the sense of curiosity.

◆ The wall art ◆ The painted corner ■ The visible space of the painted corner
◆ The sofa ■ The movement spaces ▲ The functional space of the sofa
■ The visible space of the wall art ▲ The functional space of the socket

Figure 36. A floor plan of the AU-MolBio, showing the corner, the sofa and the wall art.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
slab (S1)	occupant (P)	experience (funcI)
wall (W)	funcM = movementSpace (S1, P)	
on (W, S1)	funcV = visibleSpace (A, P)	
artwork (A)	funcI = intersection (funcM, funcV)	
on (A, W)		

Figure 37. Formalization of DI4.

DI5 - There is a coloured line of paint wrapping around the corner. The building users will feel curious about what is it around the corner, illustrated in Figure 36. This case is an example of a **basic causal relationship**. The formalization of the argument is presented in Figure 38. The formalization was performed according to the following: There is a slab (S1) representing the area where the corner (C) is located, a wall (W) installed on that slab and a line of color (CI) is painted. There is an occupant (P) who is moving inside the movement space of the slab and at the same time they are inside the visible space of the line of color. This intersection between the movement space of the slab (S1) and the visible space of the line of color (CI) creates the desired experience for the occupant (P), which is the sense of curiosity.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
wall (W1)	occupant (P)	curiosity (funcI)
wall (W2)	funcM = movementSpace (S1, P)	
color (C1)	funcV = visibleSpace (C, P)	
painted (C1, W1)	funcI = intersection (funcM, funcV)	
painted (C1, W2)		

Figure 38. Formalization of DI5.

DI6 - There is a sofa that contains electrical outlets. The students should enjoy using the space, illustrated in Figure 36. This case is an example of a **basic causal relationship**. The formalization of the argument is presented in Figure 39. The formalization was performed according to the following: There is a slab (S1) on which a sofa (S) is installed, and adjacent to that sofa, a socket (So) is also installed. There is an occupant (P), who is in the functional space of both the sofa and the socket, hence the occupant can use the space.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
slab (S1)	occupant (P)	usage (funcI)
sofa (S)	funcF1 = functionalSpace (S, P)	
on (S, S1)	funcF2 = functionalSpace (So, P)	
socket (So)	funcI = intersection (funcF1, funcF2)	
adjacent (So, S)		

Figure 39. Formalization of DI6.

DI7 - There are sofas and tables that can be used as a workplace for small meetings, online meetings and lunch. Making the building users want to come and work from office instead of working from home, illustrated in Figure 40. This case is another example of a **common-effect causal relationship**. The formalization of the argument is presented in Figure 41. The formalization was performed according to the following: There is a sofa (S) and a table (T) on a slab (S1). There is an occupant (P), who would want to use the space instead of working from home. The intersection between the functional space of the table and the functional space of the sofa creates the value. The table and the sofa contribute in achieving the intended effect.

Figure 40. A floor plan of the AU-CED. showing the tables, sofas and acoustic panels.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
sofa (S)	occupant (P)	usage (funcI)
table (T)	funcF = functionalSpace (T, P)	
slab (S1)	funcF2 = functionalSpace (S, P)	
on (S, S1)	funcI = intersection (funcF, funcF2)	
on (T, S1)		

Figure 41. Formalization of D17.

D18 - There are acoustic panels in the area to make good acoustic environment. Make the building users want to come and work from office instead of working from home, illustrated in Figure 40. This case is another example of a **basic causal relationship**. The formalization of the of the argument are presented in Figure 42Figure 39. The formalization was performed according to the following: This argument was formalized according to the following: Acoustic panels (AP) are installed on slab (S1) to create an acoustic space that would encourage the building occupant to use this area instead of working from home.

The Product Level	The Domain Level	The Goal Level
acousticPanel (AP)	occupant (P)	usage (funcA)
slab (S1)	funcA = acousticSpace (AP, P)	
on (AP, S1)		

Figure 42. Formalization of D18.

Appendix B

The complete and detailed sensitivity evaluation of air quality, heatwaves, marine submersion and strong winds, river flooding, clay swelling and shrinking, freeze-thaw and monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature for Dublin LL and Aarhus LL are presented.

Dublin LL

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Building infrastructure: County Hall, Ferry Terminal, Lexicon Library, Harbour Master's Building; Social Housing	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	Degradation of materials and corrosion	Exposure to pollutants may weaken structural integrity	3	Increased risk of deformation	High temperatures causing expansion and weakening	1	Structural damage (e.g., corrosion)	Water infiltration into the building structure may cause corrosion of structural materials over time.	2	Damage to structure	Wind pressure causing structural failure	3
	Interior finishing materials	Flooring, walls, ceilings, etc	Discoloration or damage	Chemical reactions between pollutants and materials	2	Material degradation, warping	High temperatures leading to deterioration and warping	1	Damage and mold growth	Water damage to materials and mold growth	1	Damage to finishes	Wind-borne debris causing scratches, dents	3
	Isolation system	Isolation material	Degradation of insulation properties	Loss of insulating properties due to	2	Decreased effectiveness	High temperatures reducing insulation	1	Insulation degradation	Degradation of insulation due to	1	Structural integrity	Wind pressure causing isolation damage	1

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
				contamination			effectiveness			water exposure				
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	Degradation of seals and weatherstripping	Reduced effectiveness in sealing against air infiltration	2	Warping, air leakage	High temperatures causing expansion and damage	3	Degradation	Water infiltration through gaps and seals	2	Structural integrity	Wind pressure causing seal failure	3
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	Corrosion of electrical components	Increased risk of electrical failure	2	Overheating, malfunction	High temperatures causing electrical system overload	4	Electrical system damage	Water infiltration into elevator shafts and motor rooms can damage electrical components, rendering elevators and escalators inoperable	4	Disruption	Wind-induced vibrations affecting operation	1
Utilities	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	Performance and lifespan reduction	Pollutants may impact performance and lifespan of electrical equipments, if there is not proper	2	Overheating and efficiency reduction	Overheating of equipment, leading to reduced efficiency and potential failure	3	Electrical failure	Water infiltration into electrical equipment such as transformers and switchgear, leading to short	4	Disruption	Wind-induced vibrations affecting operation	3

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
				ventilation and maintenance						circuits and equipment malfunction.				
	Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	Corrosion of pipes and fixtures	Reduced lifespan of pipes and fixtures	1	Decreased effectiveness	High temperatures reducing water flow and pressure	1	Water infiltration into pipes and drainage systems	Marine submersion can overwhelm drainage systems, causing water backup and infiltration into pipes, leading to flooding and infrastructure damage.	3	Leakage	Wind pressure causing pipe displacement	0
	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system	Air handlers, chillers, filters	Accumulation of pollutants in filters and coils	Reduced efficiency and airflow	3	Overheating, reduced efficiency	High temperatures causing HVAC system overload	3	Equipment and control damage	Water infiltration into HVAC units can damage components and controls, leading to system failures	2	Disruption	Wind-induced vibrations affecting operation	1

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	Build-up of pollutants on panels	Decreased efficiency and energy production	4	Reduced efficiency, overheating	High temperatures decreasing solar panel efficiency	3	PV and electrical components damage	Marine submersion can lead to direct contact of solar panels and electrical components with saltwater, causing corrosion, short circuits, and electrical malfunctions.	0	Damage	Wind pressure causing panel detachment	2
Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking	Corrosion of parking structure	Structural degradation and reduced lifespan	2	Pavement deformation	Softening or deformation of pavement materials, potentially leading to surface damage.	1	Structure damage	Damage to parking lots and structures from flooding	3	Damage	Wind-borne debris causing dents	2
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways	Deterioration of pavement	Increased cracking and potholes	2	Material degradation, warping	Deterioration and warping of pavement and surfaces	1	Erosion and damage	Erosion and damage from water and wave action	1	Damage	Wind-blown debris causing surface abrasion	1

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities	Corrosion of racks and fixtures	Reduced lifespan and structural integrity	3				Corrosion and damages	Corrosion and damage of facilities because of water	1	Damage	Wind pressure causing rack displacement	3
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms	Corrosion of structures and fixtures	Structural degradation and reduced lifespan	3	Overheating of passengers	High temperatures causing discomfort and health risks	2	Damage to infrastructure and systems	Marine submersion can damage transportation infrastructure such as bus stops and platforms, disrupting public transportation services.	3	Damage	Wind-borne debris causing damage	3
	Ferry Terminal	Ferry Terminal (cross-channel ferries, arrival point, transportation links)	Corrosion of terminal structures	Structural degradation and reduced lifespan	3	Overheating of the infrastructure	High temperatures causing users discomfort	2				Damage	Wind pressure causing structural failure	4
Recreational and green spaces	Parks and open spaces	Landscaping features	Damage to vegetation and soil	Reduced plant health and biodiversity	1	Drying, wilting	Dehydration and wilting of vegetation	4	Erosion and damage	Ground erosion and vegetation damage	2	Damage	Wind-borne debris causing damage	4

Dublin LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
		Recreational amenities	Deterioration of amenities	Reduced usability and aesthetic appeal	1	Overheating, discomfort	Thermal discomfort and health risks	2	Erosion and damage	Marine submersion can lead to erosion of recreational amenities, impacting the aesthetic and functional aspects of green spaces.	2	Damage	Wind pressure causing damage	4

Table 24. Complete and detailed sensitivity evaluation for air quality, heatwaves, marine submersion and strong winds for Dublin LL.

Dublin LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Building infrastructure: County Hall, Ferry Terminal, Lexicon Library, Harbour Master's Building; Social Housing	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	Structural damage	Increased water pressure causing structural instability	4	Foundation settlement, cracks in walls	Clay soil expands during wet conditions and shrinks during dry conditions, causing movement and damage to structures	2	Cracking	Expansion and contraction of materials due to freeze-thaw cycles	2	Structural damage	Extreme temperature fluctuations can cause expansion or contraction of materials, potentially leading to structural issues such as cracking or warping.	2
	Interior finishing materials	Flooring, walls, ceilings, etc	Water damage	Absorption of water leading to warping, swelling, or degradation	3	Warping, cracking	Moisture absorption and release from clay soil leads to expansion and contraction of materials, causing damage	2	Damage to finishes and surfaces	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause moisture within materials to freeze, resulting in warping, cracking, and deterioration of finishes.	3	Expansion/Contraction of materials	Interior finishes may experience damage or deterioration, necessitating periodic repairs or replacements to maintain aesthetic appeal and functionality.	0
	Isolation system	Isolation material	Water infiltration	Water seepage through cracks or gaps leading to reduced insulation	3	Gaps, misalignment	Movement of clay soil underneath isolation materials leads to shifting and misalignment	2	Degradation	Degradation of isolation materials due to freeze-thaw cycles	2	Efficiency Reduction	Extreme temperatures can reduce the effectiveness of insulation, leading to increased	4

												energy consumption for heating or cooling.		
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	Water infiltration	Poor seals allowing water penetration, leading to damage or leakage	3	Warping, gaps	Expansion and contraction of clay soil can distort and damage seals, leading to gaps and leaks	3	Leakage	Warping or cracking of seals and frames due to freeze-thaw cycles	3	Drafts	Poorly sealed doors and windows may allow cold air infiltration, leading to discomfort and energy loss	4
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	Electrical failure	Water damage to electrical components leading to malfunction	4	Misalignment, malfunction	Uneven settling of clay soil can affect the alignment and operation of electrical systems	2	Mechanical malfunctions and operational issues	Damage to electrical components due to moisture penetration from freeze-thaw cycles	1	Operation disruption	Extreme temperatures can affect the performance and lifespan of electrical components, leading to malfunctions and outages	1
Utilities	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	Electrical failure	Water damage to electrical components leading to malfunction	4	Misalignment, malfunction	Uneven settling of clay soil can affect the alignment and operation of electrical equipment	2	Electrical failure and insulation damage	Damage to electrical components due to moisture penetration from freeze-thaw cycles	4	Overheating	Low temperatures can cause electrical equipment to overheat, leading to failure or electrical fires.	4

Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	Water contamination	Infiltration of floodwater contaminating the water supply	2	Cracks, leaks	Shifting and settlement of clay soil can cause damage and movement in pipes and fixtures	2	Cracks and leaks	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause water pipes to crack or burst due to the expansion of frozen water, leading to leaks and water damage.	4	Burst pipes	Freezing temperatures can cause water in pipes to expand and burst, resulting in leaks and water damage	3
Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system	Air handlers, chillers, filters	Equipment damage	Water damage to HVAC components leading to malfunction	4	Misalignment, malfunction	Uneven settling of clay soil can affect the alignment and operation of HVAC equipment	1	Mechanical failures and decreased efficiency	Damage due to moisture penetration from freeze-thaw cycles	4	Efficiency reduction	Inadequate insulation or malfunctioning HVAC systems may result in inefficient heating or cooling, leading to discomfort and energy waste	4
Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	Equipment damage	Water damage to solar panels leading to reduced efficiency	2	Misalignment, reduced efficiency	Uneven settling of clay soil can affect the alignment and efficiency of solar panels	1				Efficiency reduction	Reduction of PV efficiency and performance	4

Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking	structural damage	Increased water pressure causing damage to parking structures	3	Surface cracking, sinking	Clay soil movement leads to damage and sinking in parking surfaces	4	Surface damage	Cracking and deterioration of parking surfaces from freeze-thaw cycles	2	Ice formation	Accumulation of ice on parking surfaces due to low temperatures, posing safety hazards	1
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways	Structural damage	Erosion and deterioration of pavement	3	Cracking, uneven surface	Clay soil movement causes cracking and unevenness in pavement surfaces	4	Cracks, potholes, and surface degradation	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause expansion and contraction of pavement materials, leading to cracking and surface deterioration	2	Cracking	Accumulation of ice on parking surfaces due to low temperatures,	1
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities	Equipment damage	Water damage to bicycle racks and storage facilities leading to corrosion or rust	1	Misalignment, instability	Uneven settling of clay soil can affect the stability and alignment of bicycle racks	4				Corrosion	Exposure to moisture and salt from de-icing agents can accelerate corrosion of metal racks	3
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms	Service disruption	Inundation of bus stops, stations and platforms leading to service disruption	2	Structural damage, sinking	Clay soil movement can cause damage and sinking in transportation	3	Structural Damage	Cracking or warping of structures from freeze-thaw cycles	3	Service disruption	Operation of public transport can be affected because of low temperatures, leading to	1

Aarhus LL

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Building infrastructure: Administrative buildings e.g., offices, academic buildings e.g., classrooms or lecture halls, libraries, etc research facilities e.g., laboratories, student accommodations e.g., student apartments	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	Degradation of materials and erosion	Air pollution may significantly impact stone materials used in buildings. Sulfur and nitrogen oxides are particularly harmful pollutants, especially in carbonate stones, leading to the formation of acids able to erode the stone surface	1	Thermal expansion and contraction	Thermal expansion and contraction of materials, leading to structural instability or even structural failure in extreme cases.	4	Structural damage	Direct exposure to saltwater can corrode and weaken structural elements, leading to collapse or compromise of building integrity	3	Damage to structure, risk of collapse	Wind pressure and dynamic forces exerted on structural elements	3

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Interieur finishing materials	Flooring, walls, ceilings, etc	Indoor air pollution	Emission of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from materials, impacting Indoor Air Quality	0	Degradation of materials	Warping, cracking, or degradation of materials due to extreme temperatures.	3	Repairable damage and mold growth	Submersion can saturate interior materials, leading to damage and mold growth, requiring cleaning and restoration	3	Damage to finishes, risk of detachment	Impact from wind-blown debris, stress on attachments	3
	Isolation system	Isolation material	Degradation of indoor air quality	Emission of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from insulation materials	1	Insulation materials effectiveness reduction	Reduction in effectiveness due to heat absorption, leading to increased energy consumption.	2				Compromised thermal performance	Disruption of insulation due to wind pressure	2
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	Indoor air pollution	Poor seals or gaps allow outdoor pollutants to enter indoor spaces, reducing Indoor Air Quality and energy efficiency.	3	Expansion or warping	Expansion or warping of frames, potentially leading to difficulty in opening or closing.	1				Risk of breakage, air infiltration	Wind pressure and impact from debris	3

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	Degradation of indoor air quality	Accumulation of dust and pollutants on electronic components, affecting performance of electric systems	3	Overheating and efficiency reduction	Overheating of equipment, leading to reduced efficiency and potential failure	1	Inoperable due to water damage	Water infiltration into elevator shafts and motor rooms can damage electrical components, rendering elevators and escalators inoperable	4	Service interruption, safety hazard	Wind-induced sway and stress on components	1
Utilities	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	Performance and lifespan reduction	Pollutants may impact performance and lifespan of electrical equipments, if there is not proper ventilation and maintenance	3	Overheating and efficiency reduction	Overheating of equipment, leading to reduced efficiency and potential failure	3	Electrical failure	Submersion can damage transformers, switchgear cabinets and electrical components, leading to power outages and electrical system failures	4	Service interruption, equipment damage	Wind pressure and impact from debris	2

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	Deterioration of water quality and health risks	Contamination of water sources due to air pollutants such as particulate matter, chemical emissions, and microbial contaminants	1	Deformation of drainage system	Expansion or contraction of pipes, potentially leading to leaks or bursts.	0	Water contamination and damage	Submersion can damage water pipes, leading to water contamination and disruptions to water supply. Besides, it can overwhelm drainage systems, causing water backup and flooding of buildings and surrounding areas	3	Damage, water loss, service disruption	Disruption of flow, stress on components	1
	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system	Air handlers, chillers, filters	Degradation in indoor air quality	Inadequate ventilation leading to accumulation of pollutants, mold, and stale air	4	Overloading of system	Overloading of systems, reduced cooling capacity, and potential system failure.	4	Inoperable due to water damage	Water infiltration into HVAC units can damage components and controls, leading to system failures and indoor air quality issues	3	Service interruption, damage	Stress on components, blockage from debris	1

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	Reduction in energy generation and efficiency	Accumulation of dust and pollutants on solar panel surfaces, reducing sunlight absorption and efficiency	3									
Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking				Pavement deformation	Softening or deformation of pavement materials, potentially leading to surface damage.	3	Flooding and damage to vehicles	Submersion can flood parking lots, damaging vehicles and infrastructure, and disrupting parking operations	3	Property damage, access disruption	Parking structures can sustain structural damage from strong winds	3
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways	Air quality deterioration	Road surfaces contribute to air pollution through vehicle emissions and particulate matter generation. Regular cleaning and maintenance are necessary to	0	Pavement deformation	Softening or deformation of pavement materials, potentially leading to surface damage. Pathways may become impassable, affecting accessibility to campus.	3	Structural damage	Submersion can erode road pavements surfaces, pathways and walkways and compromise their integrity.	4	Pavement damage	Wind-blown debris can cause pavement damage	1

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
				mitigate impacts.										
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities							Damage and displacement	Submersion can damage bike lanes and racks, posing safety hazards and impacting accessibility for cyclists	4	Access disruption, safety hazard	Wind can damage or displace bicycle racks and shelters	1

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms	Indoor air pollution, discomfort	Bus, trains and stations are enclosed spaces with potential indoor air pollution. Adequate ventilation and air quality monitoring are necessary for passenger comfort and safety.	2	Thermal discomfort	Discomfort for passengers due to lack of shade or shelter.	2	Structural damage	Submersion can erode tracks and compromise their stability, leading to railway disruptions, affecting public transportation access and safety.	2	Service interruption, access disruption	Wind can damage or displace bus shelters and stations	3
Information Technology (IT) Infrastructure	Servers systems	Servers and data storage	Overheating and damage	Exposure to air pollutants can lead to airflow obstruction, overheating and hardware malfunction	1	Overheating	Increased risk of overheating, leading to system downtime and potential data loss.	3	Data loss and system failure	Water damage to servers can lead to data loss and system failures, impacting critical operations and services	2	Equipment malfunction, data loss	Wind may cause servers to malfunction or lose connectivity	2

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Networking equipment	Networking switches and routers	Performance degradation	Dust and pollutants can accumulate on components, affecting connectivity	1	Overheating	Increased risk of overheating, leading to system downtime and potential data loss.	3	Network outages and communication failures	Water infiltration into networking equipment can cause electrical malfunctions, leading to network outages	2	Network disruption	Wind may damage networking equipment or disrupt connections	2
	Computers and peripherals	Computers (desktops, laptops)	Performance degradation	Dust buildup can affect performance and lifespan	0	Overheated equipment	Reduced performance and potential hardware damage due to overheating.	2	Inoperable due to water damage	Water damage to computers and peripherals can render them inoperable, disrupting work and communication	2	Equipment malfunction, data loss	Wind-blown debris or power outages can disrupt IT equipment	2

Aarhus LL System			Air quality			Heatwaves			Marine submersion			Strong winds		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Recreational and green spaces	Parks and open spaces	University Park, botanical and community gardens	Worseing air quality	Air pollutants such as particulate matter and ozone may be impact outside air quality, impacting users respiratory health.	3	Vegetation thermal stress	Heat stress and dehydration of vegetation, leading to wilted leaves, browning, and die-off.	4				Physical damage	Physical damage, uprooting, and breakage of branches	2
		Sports Fields	Accumulati on of air pollution	Air pollutants may accumulate over sport equipment requiring cleaning or maintenance to ensure safety.	1	Degradation of equipement comfortability	Outdoor infrastructure can be affected by heatwaves, leading to discomfort for users and potential safety concerns.	3			0	Damage of ground	Dislodging and uprooting of grass, damage to ground cover	2

Table 26. Complete and detailed sensitivity evaluation for air quality, heatwaves, marine submersion and strong winds for Aarhus LL.

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Building infrastructure: Administrative buildings e.g., offices, academic buildings e.g., classrooms or lecture halls, libraries, etc research facilities e.g., laboratories	Structural components	Beams, columns, etc	Water infiltration and structural damage	When floodwaters penetrate buildings, they can seep into structural components such as beams and columns, weakening their integrity over time. This can lead to structural instability, compromising the safety of the building occupants.	3	Structural stress and cracking	Swelling of clay soil during wet periods followed by shrinking during dry periods, causing movement.	3	Structural damage due to expansion and contraction of materials	Freeze-Thaw cycles cause moisture within materials to freeze and expand, leading to cracks and structural weakening.	4	Expansion/Contraction of materials	Temperature fluctuations can cause materials to expand or contract, potentially leading to structural issues such as cracking or warping.	3

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
				deteriorate. This can result in unsightly damage and create ideal conditions for mold growth, posing health risks to occupants.									appeal and functionality.	
	Isolation system	Isolation material	Water infiltration and degradation	Isolation materials, such as insulation and waterproof membranes, may become saturated with water during flooding events. This can lead to degradation of these materials, reducing their effectiveness and potentially compromise	3	Degradation	Swelling and shrinkage of clay soils may compress or damage insulation materials.	2	Seal failure, air leakage, and compromised insulation	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause expansion and contraction, leading to gaps, drafts, and reduced energy efficiency.	3	Efficiency Reduction	Extreme temperatures can reduce the effectiveness of insulation, leading to increased energy consumption for heating or cooling.	3

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
				ng the building's thermal performance and waterproofing.										
	Door, windows, seals	Doors, windows, seals	Water infiltration and damage	Doors and windows are vulnerable points where floodwaters can easily enter buildings. Water infiltration through gaps or cracks can damage interior finishes, furniture, and equipment, leading to costly repairs and replacements.	3	Operational issues	Swelling of surrounding clay soil may cause sticking or misalignment of doors and windows.	2						

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Electrical systems	Elevators and escalators	Water damage to electrical systems	Elevators, escalators, and fire protection systems rely on electrical components to function. Floodwaters can damage these electrical systems, causing malfunctions or complete failure, which can hinder evacuation efforts and compromise fire safety.	4	Alignment issues	Structural movement of buildings due to clay movement may indirectly affect elevator alignment	2	Mechanical malfunctions and operational issues	Freeze-Thaw cycles can affect moving parts and mechanical systems, leading to malfunctioning and increased maintenance needs.	1	Performance Degradation	Extreme temperatures can affect the performance of mechanical components, leading to increased wear and potential malfunctions	

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Utilities	Electricity distribution system	Transformers, switchgear, etc	Water infiltration/damage and electrical system malfunction/failure	Floodwaters can infiltrate transformers and switchgear, leading to electrical system failure. Water can cause short circuits, corrosion, and damage to electrical components, resulting in power outages and safety hazards.	4	Electrical damage	Structural movement may indirectly affect electrical distribution infrastructure.	0	Electrical failure and insulation damage	Moisture intrusion into electrical components due to freezing and thawing can cause short circuits and electrical fires.	4	Overheating	Low temperatures can cause electrical equipment to overheat, leading to failure or electrical fires.	4

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Water supply and drainage system	Pipes, sinks, toilets...	Water infiltration and pipe corrosion/Inadequate drainage leading to water backup and overflow	Flooding can compromise the functionality of the water supply and drainage system, affecting access to clean water and leading to water-related damage.	1	Potential for minor leaks and disruptions	Structural movement may cause stress on water pipes, leading to minor leaks and blockages of drainage systems.	1	Cracks and leaks	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause water pipes to crack or burst due to the expansion of frozen water, leading to leaks and water damage.	4	Expansion/Contraction of materials	Temperature fluctuations can cause pipes to expand or contract, potentially leading to leaks or burst pipes. Besides, it can cause freezing or thawing of drainage systems, leading to blockages and flooding.	3	
														Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) system

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Renewable energy systems	Solar panels	Water infiltration/damage	Floodwaters can damage solar panels and their associated electrical components, such as inverters and wiring. This can result in reduced energy generation, electrical system failures, and safety hazards. Additionally, floodwaters may deposit debris or sediment on solar panels, further reducing their efficiency.	1									

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System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Transportation	Roads and pathways	Parking				Potential damage of surface	Structural movement may cause minor surface irregularities, affecting vehicle parking and maneuverability.	2				Surface Damage	Extreme temperatures can cause damage to parking lot surfaces, such as cracking or deterioration of pavement materials.	2
	Parking facilities	Pathways, walkways				Potential damage	Swelling and shrinking of clay soils may cause cracks or unevenness in pavement, leading to minor damage and safety hazards.	3	Cracks, potholes, and surface degradation	Freeze-Thaw cycles can cause expansion and contraction of pavement materials, leading to cracking and surface deterioration.	2	Deterioration	Temperature fluctuations can cause pavement materials to expand, contract, or degrade, leading to cracks, potholes, or surface deterioration.	3

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
	Bicycle infrastructure	Bicycle racks and storage facilities				Potential damage of surface	Structural movement may cause minor surface irregularities.	2				Corrosion	Temperature fluctuations can accelerate corrosion of metal components, leading to structural degradation or failure.	2
	Public transportation access	Bus and train stops, platforms				Potential damage of surface	Structural movement may cause minor surface irregularities, impacting accessibility and safety.	2				Deterioration	Extreme temperatures can cause materials to degrade or fade, impacting the structural integrity and aesthetics of bus shelters.	2

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System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Information Technology (IT) Infrastructure	Servers systems	Servers and data storage				Connectivity issues	Structural movement may indirectly affect server alignment or connectivity.	0	Equipment failure and data loss	Freeze-Thaw cycles can affect server room temperatures, leading to overheating or condensation, potentially damaging hardware.	2	Performance Degradation	Extreme temperatures can affect server performance, leading to slowdowns, data loss, or hardware failures.	1
	Networking equipment	Networking switches and routers				Network damage	Structural movement may indirectly affect network connectivity.	0	Connectivity issues and hardware failures	Freeze-Thaw cycles can impact the performance and reliability of networking equipment, leading to connectivity issues.	2	Performance Degradation	Extreme temperatures can impact network equipment performance, leading to slowdowns or disruptions in connectivity.	1

Aarhus LL System			River flooding			Clay swelling and shrinking			Freeze-Thaw			Monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature		
System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
Recreational and green spaces	Computers and peripherals	Computers (desktops, laptops)							Malfunctions and hardware damage	Freeze-Thaw cycles can affect the performance and reliability of computer equipment, leading to malfunctions and data loss.	2	Performance Degradation	Extreme temperatures can cause computers to overheat, leading to slowdowns, crashes, or hardware failures.	1
	Parks and open spaces	University Park, botanical and community gardens		Excessive water saturation may lead to plant damage or loss, affecting the aesthetics of the area.					Plant health and structural damages	Freeze-Thaw cycles can damage roots, bark, and foliage, affecting plant health and longevity. Besides, it can cause tree branches to become brittle, increasing the risk of breakage and falling.	2	Plant health	Certain plant species may be sensitive to changes in temperature, leading to decreased health, growth, or survival because of frost damage to foliage and roots	0

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System	Subsystems	Component	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity	Impact	Impact mechanism	Sensitivity
		Sports Fields	Equipement' damage	Equipment may be submerged, damaged, or rendered unsafe for use, posing risks to users.	0				Ground stability	Freeze-Thaw cycles cause soil expansion and contraction, leading to soil cracking, erosion, and compaction	3	Frost damage	Susceptibility of grass to frost burn and damage	1

Table 27. Complete and detailed sensitivity evaluation for river flooding, clay swelling and shrinking, freeze-thaw and monthly mean value of daily minimum temperature for Aarhus LL.